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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

SIBILLINI MOUNTAIN RANGE, A CAVE AND LAKE TO
THE OTHERWORLD¹

PART 1

1. The meaning of a legend

A few years ago we started an exciting journey into myth and literary tradition, a travel that has led our steps partly through our material, tangible world, with a breathtaking immersion into the gorgeous scenery of the Sibillini Mountain Range, the imposing fastnesses which raise in central Italy with their high peaks and precipitous ravines, a portion of the Apennine chain; and partly, across a more elusive, particularly uncanny world which marks the same geographical feature, pertaining to the sinister

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lore that has been living for many hundreds of years amid those remote Italian cliffs.

Since the fifteenth century, people in Europe has been aware that a small portion of the land of Italy is a realm of gloomy mystery and magic. A Sibyl, the Sibyl of the Apennines, was reputed to live beneath one of the peaks that challenge the winds in that distant, inaccessible region, with her hidden court and illusory kingdom set within the enchanted space of a subterranean Cave, in which knights could be deprived of their immortal soul while experiencing a life of eternal bliss and lustful sin. A few miles away from the dark entrance to that Cave, a Lake stood, icy waters in which demons were believed to dwell, together with the dead body of Pontius Pilate, the most famous Roman prefect, the man who sentenced Jesus Christ to death, whose corpse had been magically thrown into that liquid mirror encircled by vertiginous crests.

Fig. 1 - Mount Sibyl, Sibillini Mountain Range, Italy

Two legends for the same mountain range. Two different myths, apparently marked by different traits, which lived amid the very same fastnesses, at two distinct spots. Only 5.2 miles away from one another, and in full mutual line of sight.

Fig. 2 - Lakes of Pilate, Sibillini Mountain Range, Italy, with Mount Sibyl raising in the background

And the renown of the two legends was great. For centuries visitors had pushed themselves as far as those far-away corner of Italy to meet the Sibyl and her handsome damsels at the Cave, or to consecrate their spellbooks at the Lake. Starting from Andrea da Barberino's romance *Guerrino the Wretch* and Antoine de la Sale's account *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, both legendary tales have made long journeys into many countries across Europe, so attracting knights, adventurers, necromancers, men of letters, philologists and even scientists and researchers up to the peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range, in search of a clue to a mythical truth which seemed to shun any attempt to unveil it.

Yet the time has come now for a change. Research is about to take that veil off.

Following the results of a number of preliminary studies, published between the end of the year 2017 and the first months of 2018, and including *The Knights of the Sibyl - Guerrino and his forefathers: Huon of Bordeaux*, *The Knights of the Sibyl - Guerrino and his forefathers: Huon d'Auvergne*, *Antoine de La Sale and the magical bridge concealed beneath Mount Sibyl*, *The literary truth about the magical doors in 'The Paradise of Queen Sibyl'* and *St. Patrick's Purgatory, a source for Guerrino and Antoine de La Sale*, we began to set sail for the right, proper research direction: the highlighting of the true core of the two legends.

Because the listed preliminary researches showed that selected elements in the Apennine Sibyl's legend were not original: they were drawn from other legendary traditions, especially chivalric.

This line of investigation led to further fundamental advances in the research. With the subsequent series of articles, all written in 2018 and including *The Lake of Pilatus in an antique manuscript: Pierre Bersuire, A mysterious quote from «Bishop Primus Cambilunensis» unveiled*, *A Sibyl called Cimmerian: exploring the potential link to the Apennine Sibyl* and *The Apennine Sibyl: a journey into history in search of the oracle*, we probed further into the potential origins of the legends of the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate: the outcome seemed to confirm the fact that, according to all known sources preceding the fifteenth century, no evidence of any medieval or Roman Sibyl has ever appeared to be present in that area of Italy; and, on the other hand, a sinister lore about the Lake seemed to exist already in the fourteenth century, and with no connection to the figure of Pontius Pilate.

All this research work opened the way to two landmark papers, both released in 2019, which provide a new firm starting point for all subsequent researches.

With *Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection*, we traced the lineage of the Apennine Sibyl back to the legendary material which is part of the illustrious Matter of Britain. The Sibyl of the Sibillini Mountain Range is to be acknowledged as the fairy and necromancer 'Sebile', a companion of her

most famous mate Morgan le Fay, King Arthur's half-sister. The two characters are staged in many chivalric poems and romances, and the former is the offspring of a literary comparison between Morgan and a Sibyl as mentioned by German writer Hartmann von Aue in his poem *Erec*, written at the end of the twelfth century. Literary topics like the imprisoned knight in enchanted, concealed castles fully belong to the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian cycle, and in them we find Sebile involved in many episodes and situations which can be also retrieved in the literary tradition concerning the Apennine Sibyl.

Fig. 3 - The opening image of the research paper *Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection*

With *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*, we provided no utterly new findings, for it is widely known amid scholars that the legendary tale which concerns the famous Roman prefect has been travelling throughout the centuries Middle Ages, with numerous literary witnesses and a powerful circulation of oral narratives, with the indication of many different resting places for Pilate's cursed body, all inhabited by legendary demonic presences, and with no reference at all to any legendary burial site to be retrieved within the Sibillini Mountain Range in Italy.

Fig. 4 - The opening image of the research paper *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*

The final results arising from the two articles show that the legends of the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate are local adaptations of foreign legendary tales, which were born elsewhere and developed themselves elsewhere.

Therefore, the Apennine Sibyl and the lore on Pontius Pilate are additional mythical layers which do not belong to the Sibillini Mountain Range. And the two listed layers actually shade some thing that lies beneath them: the true legendary core of the myth which inhabits this portion of the Italian Apennines.

How can we be confident that some other, deeper legendary tale lies in the background?

The decisive reason, in our view, is that no extraneous, unrelated legend can attach to a place without any attractive pull which directs it exactly to that specific spot.

A sort of magnetic influence, mythical as it may be, is needed to attract the magical tales about Sebile and Pontius Pilate to the crests of the Sibillini Mountain Range. It is not a mere fated chance the fact that the gloomy tale on the enchanted realm of a Sibyl and the sinister narrative about a Roman prefect came to rest, like a ball spinning on a roulette wheel, right into the position marked by these remote Italian mountains.

The land of Italy is scattered of hundreds of lakes, peaks and mountaintops; yet two illustrious legendary tales came to settle exactly within those fastnesses. And they established themselves in two neighbouring spots, placed only a few miles away from each other, in full line of view.

This is the fundamental issue of our whole search, the most critical one: it actually appears that both the Lakes of Pilate and the Apennine Sibyl arose from some odd condensation of a peculiar nature which marks this place, the Sibillini Mountain Range. There is a sort of original core pertaining to both myths: a legend before the legends, something that was not transplanted from any other place or tradition, something that was born right here instead, and possibly connected to the fact that this location is some sort of very special site.

What is this odd condensation about? What is the peculiar nature of this remote corner of the land of Italy?

The above considerations and questions paved the way to the latest article we released on the subject. In the paper *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends*, released in 2019, we began to look into the marks left by a potential, original, still-unknown common legendary core that may lie beneath the narratives on the Apennine Sibyl and Pontius Pilate. And the findings were utterly promising.

We highlighted a number of common traits that mark both legends, the Cave's and Lake's. And we found out at least three shared features: a legendary demonic presence; the performance of necromantic rituals; winds, tempests, and devastation which mythically arise from both sites.

For centuries, both the Cave and Lake were believed to house some sort of local legendary demons. For centuries, at both place necromancy was

carried out, with a view to conjure up fiendish presences. For centuries, the action of necromancers was believed to devastate the neighbouring territory out of the violent storms which arose from the two places.

Fig. 5 - A composite image presented in the research paper *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends*

The two sites seem actually to have something in common, in terms of legendary features. But what legend lies behind the two of them?

As we already stated in the concluding remarks of our paper *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends*, we begin to get glimpses of the original, common core of the two legends. There is something with the Cave and Lake which has nothing to do with the Apennine Sibyl and Pontius Pilate. Some thing deeper. Some thing more ancient.

We are getting closer and closer to the true nucleus of the legends that inhabit the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy. However, our journey into the mystery which lies at the core is not ended yet.

After having highlighted the three listed common traits, now we need to highlight a fourth shared aspect, which we have not yet mentioned.

This is entryway. Entryway to the Otherworld.

And we are going to explore this fundamental aspect in the present research paper.

2. Entryways to darkness

We are now about to make a further step towards the mythical core which the towering fastenings of the Sibillini Mountain Range, in central Italy, encircle and shelter. We are making our way through the layers of superimposed narratives that have enshrouded the Sibyl's Cave and the Lakes of Pilate for many centuries. Through a cloudy fog, consisting of foreign tales which tell stories of Sibyls and Roman prefects, we have started to get glimpses of the true, common core of both legends. A core that includes three shared aspects: demons, necromantic summoning, and devastation.

And we also have a fourth common trait which links the Cave and the Lake.

There are hints that the two places were considered as entryways to the Otherworld.

What are we talking about? Let's follow the clues and try to figure out their meaning.

2.1 *The Cave as a supernatural entryway*

In actual truth, what is the Sibyl's Cave, according to its own legend?

Apparently, the Cave is an access to a subterranean realm of lust and sin, ruled by a sibilline prophetess, as at first sight it presents itself when we read such works as *Guerrino the Wretch* and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*.

At first sight, this is what the Cave is. But only at a first glance.

Instead, if we proceed to a closer scrutiny of the two listed legendary narratives, we stumble upon a number of remarkable clues. Clues which lead our investigation towards different, unprecedented directions.

In our previous paper *Antoine de la Sale and the magical bridge concealed beneath Mount Sibyl*, we confronted with the enchanted bridge that, according to the narrative set down by the fifteenth-century French visitor Antoine de la Sale, rested in the baleful darkness of the Sibyl's Cave:

«Then you find a bridge, made of some unknown material, but it is said to be less than a single foot wide and it seems to be extending far ahead. Below the bridge, a ghastly, precipitating abyss [...] Yet as soon as you put both feet on the bridge, it becomes large enough; and the more you step ahead, the more it widens and the abyss becomes shallower».

[In the original French text: «Lors trouve-l'on ung pont, que on ne scet de quoy il est, mais est advis qu'il n'est mie ung pied de large et semble estre moult long. Dessoubz ce pont, a très grant et hydeux abisme de parfondeur [...] Mais aussitost que on a les deux pieds sur le pont, il est assez large; et tant va on plus avant et plus est large et moins creux»].

As we already detailed in the above-mentioned research paper, Antoine de la Sale's bridge is a highly significant piece of narration: because this is no ordinary bridge at all, nor even a fanciful literary contrivance to be ascribed to the imagination of the experienced French courtier. The magically thin bridge, which widens as the true believer in God treads on it backed by his sincere faith, belongs to the antique tradition of the 'test bridges' used for the judgment of souls in the afterlife world.

Fig. 6 - The magical bridge as portrayed in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 10v)

It is a literary device we meet in legendary tales that depict journeys to the Otherworld.

In that research paper, we comprehensively presented the illustrious lineage of the magically narrow bridge: it appears in the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, a twelfth-century account of a travel into a hellish Purgatory set in Ireland, thriving with demons and damned souls; it appears in the *Vision of St. Adamnán*, an eleventh-century account of the same kind; it appears in a number of similar visionary travels, including the *Vision of Alberic* (twelfth century), the *Vision of Tnugdalus* (another twelfth century text), the *Vision of Sunniulf*, and then the *Vision of Ezra*; and it appears in a most ancient narrative, the *Dialogues* written by Pope St. Gregory I the Great in the sixth century, a visionary description of a journey into the afterlife.

As we will see in later paragraphs, all such visions stage a mortal man, often a knight or a soldier, who is given the chance to behold the sufferings of the damned through a visit carried out into an otherworldly afterlife, which is accessed in a dream, or even through a cave, like in the case of the Purgatory of St. Patrick. On coming back to the ordinary world, he will be able to warn the living beings about the unbearable punishments that loom on the sinner and the unrepentant in the Otherworld.

Is the same device present in *Guerrino the Wretch* as well? Yes and no, at the same time. Because, even though Andrea da Barberino does not include any such bridge in his description of the Sibyl's subterranean realm, in the subsequent chapters he sends the hero Guerrino right into the Purgatory of St. Patrick, in Ireland, as a penance for his visit to the forbidden court of the Sibyl. And there, within the Purgatory, amid the souls of the damned and the vision of excruciating tortures, the magically narrow bridge is staged not once, but twice. In the first instance, Guerrino confronts successfully with the bridge:

«... and immediately he was standing on a bridge that crossed the marsh from one side to the other over a large river. And it seemed to him that the bridge was so narrow that nobody could have put one foot ahead of the other. He turned to get back but he could not see the bridge beneath his own eyes. And he saw countless jaws of big snakes and dragons, and it was as if they were waiting for him to fall down. Guerrino had never been so scared as in this predicament. And all the way along the bridge he feared he would fall. And actually he was about to fall: but he called on the Holy Name, and by His mercy the bridge swell to a huge width. And he could go through this perilous passage».

[In the original Italian text: «... e subito fu drito sopra uno ponte che trapassava questo lagune da uno lato al altro sopra uno grande fiume. E parevali questo ponte tanto sottile, che uno piede avanti l'altro non li poteva stare. Lui se volse per tornare e non vide el ponte abasso gli ochi. E vide infinite bocche de grandi serpenti, e dragoni, e pareva che aspetassero che lui cadesse. Anchora non havea avuto Guerino maggior paura che questa. E tutta via li pareva de cadere. E pure saria caduto: ma chiamò el santo nome, e per la soa misericordia el ponte se li fece larghissimo. E passò de là da questo fortunoso passo»].

In the second instance, placed by the author a few chapters ahead, the same episode undergoes a repetition:

«And he saw a river that was crossed by so thin and narrow a bridge that there was no small animal that would pass through it, because of his tiny width. He crossed himself and entrusted himself to God. He was taken [by the demons] and placed onto the middle of the bridge, where they left him,

then they began to scream at him, and flung stones and shafts at him so that he was about to fall. And he turned to go back, and could see no bridge. So he looked at the bottom where the water was, and saw that it was full of hideous worms and snakes. The bridge was so thin that it was not possible to put one foot ahead of the other. He began to call the name of Jesus Christ of Nazareth, and the bridge started to get larger. As he spoke these words thrice, he began to sing 'Domine ne in furore tuo arguas me', and the bridge became even larger, and he was through».

Fig. 7 - *Guerrino the Wretch*, the two different excerpts where the knight Guerrino encounters the same magical bridge (form the 1480 edition printed in Venice)

[In the original Italian text: «e vide uno fiume cui atraverso li era uno ponte tanto sutile e stretto che lo non è si piccolo animale che havesse potuto passare, tanto era stretto. Lui se fece el segno de la santa croce e recomandose a dio. Fu preso [dai demoni] e posto suxo el mezo del ponte et ivi lo lassorono, e poi cominciarono a cridare et a zitarli pietre e pali per modo che el meschino fu per cadere. E lui se volse indietro per tornare indietro, e non vide ponte. Allora pose mente nel fundo de laqua, e lo vide pieno de vermini bruti e serpenti. El ponte era si stretto che uno pié inanti l'altro non li cadeva. Lui cominciò a chiamare iesu christo nazareno, e lo ponte si cominciò a largare. E dite queste parole tre volte, cominciò a cantare 'Domine ne in furore tuo arguas me', et el ponte se largava, e lui passò»].

In *Guerrino the Wretch*, the test bridge is encountered in the harrowing setting of the Purgatory of St. Patrick, during an otherworldly travel. The

same bridge is presented by Antoine de la Sale as placed within the Sibyl's Cave, with the same features as typically used in other otherwordly narratives dating to the Middle Ages.

Is the Sibyl's Cave an entryway to some sort of Otherworld?

The suspicion can only increase if we consider the other otherwordly device we meet in Antoine de la Sale's description, the ever-slamming doors:

«... within that cave, up to the metal doors, which slam ceaselessly day and night, opening wide and then shutting close again [...] in the cavern, there are two doors made of metal, slamming day and night without rest [...] These doors slam so savagely that everyone who wishes to enter is made aware that nobody can get in without being caught between them and crushed like a small fly. And that was what frightened them the more...».

Fig. 8 - The ever-slamming metal doors which are found within the Sibyl's Cave according to Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folia 11r and 12r)

[In the original French text: «... dedans ceste cave, jusques es portes de metall, qui jour et nuyt et sans ceser battent, cloant et ouvrant [...] à l'endroit de la cave, sont les deux portes de metal, qui jour et nuyt batent sans cesser [...] Ces portes batent par telle maniere qu'il est proprement advis à celluy qui entrer y doit, qu'il n'y pourroit entrer sans estre entre deux cueilly et tout effroissé comme une mousche. Et ce fut la chose qui le plus espouvanta...»].

In another paper, *The literary truth about the magical doors in "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl"*, we showed that this contrivance, too, is a typical device which is found in narratives of journeys to the Otherworld.

An impressive instance is contained in the eleventh-century *Vision of St. Adamnán*:

Fig. 9 - The excerpt on the ever-clashing veils of fire and ice contained in the *Vision of St. Adamnán* (manuscript no. 23 E 25 *Leabhar na hUdhré* or *Book of the Dun Cow*, Royal Irish Academy Library, Dublin, Ireland, folium 28)

«In the main doorway of the city they are confronted by a veil of fire and a veil of ice, smiting perpetually one against the other. The noise and din of these veils, as they clash together, are heard throughout the world, and the seed of Adam, should they hear that din, would be seized thereat with trembling and intolerable dismay».

[In the original Irish text: «Fíal tened ocus fíal d'aigriud i prímdorus inna cathrac inna fíadnaisse...»]

A similar image is also contained in Publius Vergilius Maro's *Aeneid*, when the poet portrays the ghastly gates to the otherworldly Tartarus (Book VI, vv. 552-556 and 570-573):

«A gate fronts it, vast, with adamantine pillars, [...] an iron tower rises into the air, and seated before it, Tisiphone, clothed in a blood-wet dress, keeps guard of the doorway, sleeplessly, night and day [...] Tisiphone the avenger, armed with her whip, without rest lashes and hits the guilty sinners».

[In the original Latin text: «Porta adversa ingens, solidoque adamante columnae, [...] stat ferrea turris ad auras, Tisiphoneque sedens, palla succincta cruenta, vestibulum exsomnia servat noctesque diesque, [...] Continuo sontes ultrix accincta flagello Tisiphone quatit insultans»].

Fig. 10 - The gates of Tartarus as they appear in Publius Vergilius Maro's *Aeneid* (manuscript Vat Lat 3225, Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 50v)

In the paper mentioned above, we quoted from A. K. Coomaraswamy's fascinating essay *Symplegades*, in which the renowned scholar effectively portrays the nature of the mythical clashing barriers: «whoever would transfer from this to the Otherworld, or return, must do so through the undimensioned and timeless "interval" that divides related but contrary forces, between which, if one is to pass at all, it must be "instantly". The passage is, of course, that which is also called the "strait gate" and the "needle's eye." [These are] contraries, of which the operation is "automatic" [...] It is, then, precisely from these "pairs" that liberation must be won, from their conflict that we must escape, if we are to be freed from our mortality and to be as and when we will: if, in other words, we are to reach the Farther Shore and Otherworld».

In the Cave of the Apennine Sibyl we also find a further element which seems to hint to an otherworldly character of the place. Because after the ever-slamming doors, Antoine de la Sale writes that the visitor would behold a magnificent chamber:

«They saw a rich, gorgeous door, fully resplendent out of the brightness they sent out. And the same way shone the cave, just as if it were made of crystal».

[In the original French text: «Ilz virent une tresbelle et riche porte, tresreluisant, a la clarté que ilz portoient; et mesmement reluisoit la cave, tout ainsi que c'elle feust de cristal»].

Fig. 11 - An otherworldly room in the Sibyl's Cave as described by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 13v)

But crystal rooms, supernaturally dazzling and impossible to build in our physical world, are a typical feature that marks various otherworldly narratives. In the *Book of Enoch*, an ancient Hebrew text dating to the first centuries which precede the Christian era, Enoch the Patriarch is brought to Heaven in a dream, during which he experiences otherworldly visions (Book of Dream Visions, Chapter XIV). We read the relevant passage from the transcript provided by R. H. Charles (London, 1952):

«In the vision clouds invited me and a mist summoned me [...] and the winds in the vision caused me to fly and lifted me upward, and bore me into heaven. And I went in till I drew nigh to a wall which is built of crystals and surrounded by tongues of fire; and it began to affright me. And I went into the tongues of fire and drew nigh to a large house which was built of crystals: and the walls of the house were like a tessellated floor made of crystals and its groundwork was of crystal».

And the same element also appears in the *Vision of St. Adamnán*, an Irish otherworldly text dating back to the High Middle Ages which we will analyse later in the present paper. In it, we find a description of the city in which the throne of the Lord is set:

«Seven crystal walls of various hue surround the city, each wall higher than the wall that is before it. The floor, moreover, and the lowest base of that city, is of fair crystal, with the sun's countenance upon it, shot with blue, and purple, and green, and every hue beside».

[In the original Irish text: «Ocus secht múir glainide co n-dathaib.....»].

Fig. 12 - Supernatural walls of crystal from the *Vision of St. Adamnán* (manuscript no. 23 E 25 *Leabhar na hUidhre* or *Book of the Dun Cow*, Royal Irish Academy Library, Dublin, Ireland, folium 28)

So, the Sibyl's Cave seems to house literary elements which belong to a very specific legendary tradition: a tradition which concerns the Otherworld, and the travels of mortals into Purgatory and Hell. Very special travels, by which mortal men can enter forbidden realms, and get in touch with the dead and other otherworldly entities.

We will later see that this connection is further confirmed by the strong links which can be highlighted between the Cave in which the Apennine Sibyl lives and two most-famous otherworldly narratives: that concerning the Purgatory of St. Patrick, with its lake and cave, and the other which pertains to the Cumaean Sibyl, again with her lake and cave.

But let's leave for a moment the Sibyl's Cave, and let's turn our attention to the other legendary site which is found in the Sibillini Mountain Range: the Lake of Pilate. We will try to see whether these waters, too, may be connected to an entryway to the Otherworld.

And the answer will be no surprise to us.

2.2 The waters as an access to Hell

Is the Lake of Pilate a legendary entryway to a supernatural world, the way we are beginning to guess with relation to its neighbouring site, the Sibyl's Cave?

We know that, according to the legend, the waters surrounded by the crests of Mount Vettore were considered to be one of the burial places of Pontius Pilate, and that necromancers came there to consecrate their spellbooks by summoning demons who were believed to live in the Lake.

But is that all?

No, there is more to it. The Lake was also something different.

We must remember, as we detailed in our previous paper *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*, that a resting place housing the cursed corpse of Pontius Pilate was no ordinary site: demons always were

in there, be it the river Tiber in Rome or the Rhône in France. And when the dead body of the Roman prefect was finally thrown into an abyss or pit set amid the Alps, the nature of the place was clear to all, as described in the twelfth-century poem *De Vita Pilati*:

«A place is amid the Alps, as is recorded
from which direful flames visibly erupt.
They dragged Pilate and cast him into it
to be consumed by the fire of Hell, as he deserved.
Often the voices of demons can be heard there,
fiends who rejoice of the death and punishments of the damned».

[In the original Latin text:

«Alpibus in mediis locus est, sicut memoratur
horripens et flammis a se proferre probatur
In quem Pilatum traxerunt praecipitandum
atque gehennali, sicut decet, igne cremandum.
Vox ibi multotiens auditur daemoniorum
gaudia sunt quorum mors et poenae miserorum»].

Fig. 13 - Pontius Pilate's burial place in the Alps from which hellish flames erupt (*De Vita Pilati*, manuscript LIP 51, Leiden University, folium 117v)

So Pilate's burial place in the Alps is a hole through which Hell can be accessed. Actually, an entryway to Hell. And, a century later, the same mythical idea is re-stated in Jacobus de Varagine's *Legenda Aurea* as well:

«They hurled the body into a certain pit set amid the mountains, from which people say that deceptive illusions created by the demons are visible in their agitation still today».

[In the original Latin text: «In quodam puteo montibus circumsepto immerserunt, ubi adhuc relatione quorundam quaedam dyabolicae machinationes ebullire videntur»].

Fig. 14 - A demonic pit for Pontius Pilate from the *Legenda Aurea* (manuscript NAL 1747, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 93v)

A pit, in which demons live. A hole or abyss, inhabited by a demonic presence. A physical point of contact between our world and the Otherworld.

But what about the Lake of Pilate? Does it show the same sort of character as an entryway to otherworldly places?

Yes, this is actually the case. And the supernatural nature of the Lake is stated in the famous excerpt which is found in Petrus Berchorius'

Reductorium Morale, written in the fourteenth century and not related to the legendary narrative pertaining to Pontius Pilate. Here is what Berchorius says about the hellish nature of the Lake set in the Sibillini Mountain Range:

«We may say, if you want from a symbolic point of view, that this lake means Hell, namely a place and a lake assigned to demons [...] they descend alive into Hell».

[In the original Latin text: «Dic si vis allegorice quod iste lacus significat infernum, qui est locus et lacus demonibus deputatus [...] Descendunt in infernum viventes»].

Fig. 15 - The Lake of Norcia as described in the “Reductorium Morale” by Petrus Berchorius (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Latin 16786, folium 301v)

In this passage, Petrus Berchorius is quoting from a most famous psalm (*The Holy Bible*, Book of Psalms, 55:15):

«Let death seize upon them, and let them go down alive into hell: for wickedness is in their dwellings, and among them».

[In the Latin version: «Veniat mors super illos, et descendant in infernum viventes, quoniam nequitiae in habitaculis eorum, in medio eorum»].

So the Lake of Pilate, just like the Sibyl's Cave, appears to be marked as a possible legendary entryway to the Otherworld: a place set in our physical world through which a supernatural realm can be accessed. A site which seems to put in contact mortal men with the demons, the dead, and Hell.

Fig. 16 - The drawing of the territory of today's Sibillini Mountain Range dating to the sixteenth century (manuscript Vat Lat 5241, Vatican Apostolic Library, folia 9v and 10r)

And it is not by a mere chance that, in a sixteenth-century manuscript preserved at the Vatican Apostolic Library in Rome (Vat Lat 5241), an amazing drawing is found, sketched by an anonymous hand: a diagram which portrays the territory of the Sibillini Mountain Range as it appeared more than four hundred years ago, with the towns of Norcia and Montemonaco, the small hamlet of Castelluccio, Mount Sibyl, and the Lakes of Pilate.

But, in the drawing, the Lakes are not named after the famous Roman prefect. A different name is written by their deep waters marked with black ink. And the words say «the Lake of Avernus of Norcia» (in the original Italian text: «il laco averno di Norcia»).

Fig. 17 - The Lakes set in the Sibillini Mountain Range as depicted in the sixteenth-century diagram found in manuscript Vat Lat 5241 (folium 9v)

The Lake of Avernus: the mysterious waters set near Cumae, in the Italian province of Campania, in the magical realm of the Cumaean Sibyl. Where the entryway to the House of Hades stood in antiquity.

Once more, we will see in later paragraphs that the Lake's character as an access to a supernatural world will earn additional confirmations when we will compare our Lake with the legendary narratives concerning the Lake of Avernus, linked to the Cumaean Sibyl as recalled above, and Lough Derg, the Irish setting of the legend of St. Patrick's Purgatory: both narratives tell mythical tales of access points, from our physical world, to the afterlife and the Otherworld.

Thus, we are getting nearer and nearer to a far-reaching assumption: the Sibyl's Cave and the Lakes of Pilate are not the mere setting for legendary tales which narrate of a sibilline prophetess and a Roman prefect.

There is more to it. Much more. In times which are now lost amid the mists of history, the two sites have been possibly considered as entryways: places through which mortal men could access an Otherworld that is normally forbidden to living beings.

The Cave and the Lake as legendary contact points. At those points, life and death can get in touch.

This is the working assumption we will try to explore in the present paper with a view to ascertain whether it may be rooted in any additional, firmer ground. To carry out this investigation, we need to make a special journey into the antique literary tradition concerning the legendary travels of mortal beings into the Otherworld. And we are now about to explore this fascinating, though blood-curdling, ancient tradition.

3. A passageway to the other side

Men have always been dreaming, and their dreams have often imagined the semblance of the other side: divinity, and afterlife.

The tormenting dread of death, the yearning for a vision of what is to be found beyond life, the impious desire to speak to the dead for love or divination, the craving for forbidden wishes, all that fostered the emergence of legendary tales on the journeys of mortal men into the Otherworld, in the form of poems and narratives. A manifestation of the deepest, most unfathomable fears rooted in the human soul.

The Otherworld: a place where the dead live their life after earthly life. A special, legendary sort of life, which can be either a mere life of shadows, like in classical, pre-Christian narratives, or a harrowing experience of punishments, typical of medieval visionary descriptions, in which demons play a major role and the horrified visitors are requested to watch, go back

to their fellow-men and tell the tale of the sufferings of the damned, as a warning to the living.

Fig. 18 - *The Cumaean Sibyl leads Aeneas to the underworld*, an etching by Arnold Houbraken (1660 – 1719) preserved at The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York

When imagining an Otherworld, an entryway must be also imagined: a point of passage from our world, the world of the living, and the other side, the land of divinity, demons and the dead.

And this entryway can be the stage of two different narrative situations: it can be used as a communications point to address the uncanny, blood-curdling beings who live inside, by the use of necromantic practices, yet without any attempt to initiate a ghastly travel into the inner regions; or, it may become the appalling starting point of a thoroughly horrifying journey into the darkness of the Otherworld, often a subterranean Underworld or Netherworld. In classical antiquity, the former was called a 'nekyia', the latter a 'katabasis'.

In the following paragraphs, we will retrace the main instances of otherworldly narratives from classical antiquity to the Middle Ages, limiting our review to a few examples which are part of the Western culture. It is out of the scope of the present research paper to elaborate a comprehensive essay on the subject, a task for which we cannot claim to have an adequate scientific expertise, as most illustrious scholars have addressed the topic in past and recent years.

In the present work, we only intend to highlight the main traits of the myths concerning the travels to the Otherworld in the Western tradition, with a view to assess the assumption we proposed in the previous paragraphs: do the legends which live in the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range have the character of mythical tales concerning passageways to and points of contacts with an Otherworld? Are we confronting with some sort of 'nekyia' or 'katabasis', which was carried out in antiquity at these sites set in the central Apennines, in Italy?

Fig. 19 - The region of the Sibillini Mountain Range, with an imposing view of Mount Vettore

We already saw that legendary demons are present at both the Sibyl's Cave and Pilate's Lake, and necromantic rituals are performed at the two sites, and magical doors and bridges are there which are usually found in otherworldly narratives, and some kind of access to Hell seems to be present as well.

Is all that enough to confirm that the Cave and Lake have ever been considered as entryways to an Otherworld? And what sort of Otherworld would they provide an access to?

Let's see what a journey into the Otherworld was for ancient Greeks and Romans, and for early Christians and then for the men of the Middle Ages. And we will find the key we are so eagerly looking for.

3.1 Odysseus at the gates of darkness

«... I [Odysseus] poured a libation to all the dead,
first with milk and honey, thereafter with sweet wine,
and in the third place with water, and I sprinkled thereon white barley meal.
And I earnestly entreated the powerless heads of the dead [...]
When with vows and prayers I had made supplication to the tribes of the
dead,
I took the sheep and cut their throats over the pit,
and the dark blood ran forth. Then there gathered
from out of Erebus the spirits of those that are dead,
brides, and unwedded youths, and toil-worn old men,
and tender maidens with hearts yet new to sorrow,
and many, too, that had been wounded with bronze-tipped spears,
men slain in fight, wearing their blood-stained armour.
These came thronging in crowds about the pit from every side,
with a wondrous cry; and pale fear seized me».

This is the most famous episode of the summoning of the dead, performed by Odysseus in Book XI of Homer's *Odyssey* (lines 26-29 and 34-43): the most antique example of a 'nekyia', a necromantic ritual performed at a very special site, with the shades of the dead conjured up from the House of Hades, the Otherworld of classical antiquity.

In Homer's ancient legendary account, the entryway to Hades is situated in a mythical, far-away region (lines 13 - 19): «she [Odysseus' ship] came to deep-flowing Oceanus that bounds the Earth - where is the land and city of the Cimmerians - wrapped in mist and cloud. Never does - the bright sun look down on them with his rays - either when he mounts the starry heaven - or when he turns again to earth from heaven, - but baneful night is spread over wretched mortals».

A gloomy place, a mysterious land which is the perfect setting for a point of passage between the world of the living and the realm of the dead. A

place that an antique tradition, as reported by Pliny the Elder, Strabo and Lycophrone of Chalcis, sets in the region of Cumae, at the Lake of Avernus, in the realm of the Cumaean Sibyl (see our previous article *A Sibyl called Cimmerian: exploring the potential link to the Apennine Sibyl*). It is in the land of the Cimmerians that Odysseus summons a long theory of deceased men and women (lines 51, 55, 83-84):

«The first to come was the spirit of my comrade Elpenor [...] When I saw him I wept, and my heart had compassion on him [...] Thus we two sat and held sad converse one with the other, I on one side holding my sword over the blood, while on the other side the phantom of my comrade spoke at large...».

Fig. 20 - The opening of Book XI of Homer's *Odyssey* and the lines 26-29 and 34-43 as taken from fifteenth-century manuscript Harley MS 6325 (British Museum, folia 92r and 92v)

Odysseus is following the advice provided to him by Circe, the goddess and enchantress proficient in the art of necromancy, in the preceding Book (Book X, lines 526 - 530):

oracular answers to those who know how to query them, after the performance of the right rituals.

Is that what may have occurred, in antiquity, at the Cave and Lake set within the Sibillini Mountain Range, where we know that necromancy was actually performed, and legendary fiendish presences were conjured up and addressed?

At the present stage of our investigation, we still don't know. In the *Odyssey*, necromantic arts are used to summon the souls of the dead, not the demonic beings that we know from the tradition which pertains to the Sibillini Mountain Range. And yet, we will subsequently see that demons will also make their appearance in the visionary narratives concerning the Otherworld, when we will begin to consider the visions of the still-to-come Christian era.

Nonetheless, we already know from Homer that the summoning of otherworldly entities, as carried out at the special passageway which is accessible to living men, is a highly dangerous task, as Odysseus himself discovers to his utmost terror (lines 632 - 637):

«Then the myriad tribes of the dead came thronging up - with a wondrous cry, and pale fear seized me, - lest august Persephone might send forth upon me - from out the house of Hades the head of the Gorgon, that awful monster. - Straightway then I [Odysseus] went to the ship and bade my comrades themselves - to embark, and to loose the stern cables». And he fled.

Odysseus never dared to go through that passageway and start his own 'katabasis', an actual travel into the Otherworld. He just limited himself to stepping as far as the entrance, to conjure up the shadows of the dead.

But the terror he experienced in his heart was overwhelming enough. You don't need to penetrate into the Otherworld to feel its power. And, possibly, the whole narrative might be a hint to what used to happen, perhaps, amid the precipitous cliffs of the Sibillini Mountain Range: a guess we will try to explore in further detail in the next paragraphs.

Fig. 22 - The shades of the dead drink the ritual blood in the sixteenth-century print *Ulysses at the Entrance of Hades* by Johannes Stradanus (Jan van der Straet) preserved at the Museum Boijmans Van Beuningen, Rotterdam, The Netherlands

Because it is undeniable that, since the earliest ages of the history of Western culture, tales are found of legendary passageways to the Otherworld, and necromancy, and summoning of entities, and oracular responses. A number of aspects that are also present in the legendary tales which enshroud the Sibillini Mountain Range. Specific traits, which seem to indicate that some kind of otherworldly entryway was believed to exist amid the peaks of the central Apennines, in a remote, secluded region of the land of Italy.

3.2 Aeneas and a journey into the realm of the dead

Legendary tales of passageways into the Otherworld. Fascinating narratives in which mortal men push themselves as far as mythical entryways to gloomy realms. Sinister dreams that tell the tale of a craving which haunts the soul of men since the ages of antiquity: the craving for a contact to the

other side, be it a region of the dead, divinity or the demons. A craving that, we are beginning to suppose, might have also found an abode, for reasons which are still unknown, but we are on our way to understand, at a Cave and Lake set within the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy.

In the previous paragraph, we explored the most ancient literary description which is known to us of a 'nekyia', the summoning of the shadows of the dead at the entrance of the gloomy realm of Hades, as provided to us by Homer in Book XI of his *Odyssey*.

A second illustrious description of a passageway into the Otherworld is found in Book VI of Publius Vergilius Maro's *Aeneid*, dating to the first century B.C.: a true 'katabasis', in which the main hero, Aeneas, is led into the realm of the dead by the Cumaean Sibyl, an oracular prophetess who, as we already know and will further investigate in the next paragraphs, shows a connection to the legendary narrative of the Apennine Sibyl as an oracle and seer.

Fig. 23 - Aeneas treads his first steps into the Otherworld (*Aeneid*, Book VI, lines 273 - 294), a seventeenth-century print by Franz Cleyne included in the work *Publii Virgilii Maronis Bucolica, Georgica et Aeneis* edited by John Baskerville in Birmingham in 1757

According to the tradition reported by Vergilius, the entryway to the Otherworld is located in Cumae, in the Italian province of Campania, a land whose mighty mythical power is linked to the amazing volcanic nature of the territory, as we detailed in our previous article *A Sibyl called Cimmerian: exploring the potential link to the Apennine Sibyl*.

And, according to Vergilius, the gatekeeper is the Cumaean Sibyl herself:

«One thing I [Aeneas] ask: for they say the gate of the King of Darkness is here, and the shadowy marsh, Acheron's overflow: let me have sight of my dear father, his face: show me the way, open wide the sacred doors [...] since you are all power, not for nothing has Hecate set you to rule the groves of Avernus».

[In the original Latin text (lines 106-109 and 117-118):

«Unum oro: quando hic inferni ianua regis dicitur, et tenebrosa palus Acheronte refuso, ire ad conspectum cari genitoris et ora contingat; doceas iter et sacra ostia pandas [...] potes namque omnia, nec te nequiquam lucis Hecate praefecit Avernis»].

Fig. 24 - The opening of Vergil's *Aeneid* and the excerpts on Aeneas' plea to the Sibyl as taken from the ninth-century manuscript Latin 7926 (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, folia 55v and 123v-124r)

It is Hecate, the Greek goddess associated to witchcraft and necromancy who presides over the passageways to the realm of the dead, who has appointed the Cumaean Sibyl as the gatekeeper to the Otherworld: «The path to hell is easy», she tells Aeneas, «black Pluto's door is open night and day» (in the original Latin text, lines 126-127: «facilis descensus Averno - noctes atque dies patet atri ianua Ditis»), even though she warns the Trojan hero that return is not as easy.

So she teaches Aeneas how to find the entryway. And the way in is through a dark cavern set by a lake, Lake Avernus, which lies not far from the other cave in which the Cumaean Sibyl herself dwells:

«Then [...] they reached the foul jaws of stinking Avernus [...] There was a deep stony cave, huge and gaping wide, sheltered by a dark lake and shadowy woods, over which nothing could extend its wings in safe flight, since such a breath flowed from those black jaws, and was carried to the over-arching sky, that the Greeks called it by the name Aornos, that is Avernus, or the Bird-less».

Fig. 25 - The passage on the Lake Avernus from Vergil's *Aeneid* as it appears in the most precious fourth-century manuscript Vat Lat 3225 (Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 46v)

[In the original Latin text (lines 201 and 237-242):
 «Inde ubi venere ad fauces grave olentis Averno [...] Spelunca alta fuit vastoque immanis hiatu, scrupea, tuta lacu nigro nemorumque tenebris, quam super haud ullae poterant impune volantes tendere iter pennis—talis sese halitus atris

faucibus effundens supera ad convexa ferebat:
unde locum Grai dixerunt nomine Aornon»].

The Lake Avernus is still extant today, in our present days, with all its mythical charge and fascinating legends. In ancient times, according to Strabo, the Greek geographer and historian, who writes his *Geographica* not many decades after the *Aeneid*, recounts that the Lake Avernus was «entirely encircled by ridges above, looming on it from every side but at a single point; it is now cultivated, however in old times it was enshrouded by an inaccessible wood made of huge trees, which covered with gloomy, superstitious shade the whole lake».

Fig. 26 - The Lake Avernus, set in the territory of Cumae, southern Italy, as it appears today

It is by the gloomy, blood-curdling cavern protected by that lake that the passageway to the Otherworld is to be found. And it is the Cumaean Sibyl who performs the necromantic rituals that foster the opening of the gates to the realm of the dead, with gestures which remind us of the rituals depicted by Homer in his *Odyssey* many centuries earlier:

«Here the priestess first of all tethered four black heifers,
poured wine over their foreheads [...]
calling aloud to Hecate, powerful in Heaven and Hell.

Others slit the victim's throats and caught the warm blood in bowls [...]

Then he kindled the midnight altars for the Stygian King, and placed whole carcasses of bulls on the flames, pouring rich oil over the blazing entrails».

[In the original Latin text (lines 243-244, 247-249 and 252-254):

«Quattuor hic primum nigrantis terga iuencos constituit, frontique invergit vina sacerdos [...] voce vocans Hecaten, Caeloque Ereboque potentem. Supponunt alii cultros, tepidumque cruorem suscipiunt pateris [...]

Tum Stygio regi nocturnas inchoat aras, et solida imponit taurorum viscera flammis, pingue superque oleum infundens ardentibus extis»].

Fig. 27 - A gorgeous miniature dating to the fourth century showing the necromantic rituals being performed by the Cumaean Sibyl at the Lake Avernus (Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 46v)

As a result of a ghastly necromantic art, a mighty commotion of the whole earth ensues. And the gates of the Otherworld get wide open:

«See now, at the dawn light of the rising sun,
the ground bellowed under their feet, the wooded hills began
to move, and, at the coming of the Goddess, dogs seemed to howl
in the shadows».

[In the original Latin text (lines 255-258):
«Ecce autem, primi sub lumina solis et ortus,
sub pedibus mugire solum, et iuga coepta moveri
silvarum, visaeque canes ululare per umbram,
adventante dea»].

Fig. 28 - The commotion of the earth during the necromantic rituals for the opening of the passage to the Otherworld as depicted by Vergil in his *Aeneid* (manuscript Vat Lat 3225, Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 46v)

The passageway is now open. And we will need to remember the above impressive excerpt taken from Vergilius' *Aeneid*, as it will play an astounding, fundamental role in the interpretation of one of the main common traits we identified in our previous paper *Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends* as marking both the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate in the Sibillini Mountain Range's legendary tale: the tempests and devastation which used to be stirred by necromancy performed at the two sites in the Italian Apennines. A remarkable trait, which was already present in the poem written by Publius Vergilius Maro fifteen centuries before Petrus Berchorius and Antoine de la Sale made their own written references to similar occurrences.

But let's skip this major point for the time being, and follow Aeneas and the Cumaean Sibyl as they advance into the passageway between the world of mortals and the Otherworld, and into the gloomy cavern of the dead:

«Let me reveal things buried in the deep earth, and the darkness.
On they went, hidden in solitary night, through gloom,
through Dis's empty halls, and insubstantial kingdom,
like a path through a wood, in the faint light
under a wavering moon, when Jupiter has buried the sky
in shadow, and black night has stolen the colour from things».

[In the original Latin text (lines 266-272):

«sit numine vestro
pandere res alta terra et caligine mersas.
Ibant obscuri sola sub nocte per umbram,
perque domos Ditis vacuas et inania regna:
quale per incertam lunam sub luce maligna
est iter in silvis, ubi caelum condidit umbra
Iuppiter, et rebus nox abstulit atra colorem»].

Fig. 29 - Another fourth-century miniature which portrays Aeneas as he enters the gloomy realm of the dead, together with the relevant lines (266 - 272) from Vergil's *Aeneid* (manuscript Vat Lat 3225, Vatican Apostolic Library, folium 47v)

There, the Cumaean Sibyl leads Aeneas through the shadows of the dead, until they get through the gloom and to the Fields of Elysium: an encounter with Anchises, Aeneas' father, will occur, and the glory of the Rome-to-come will be revealed to the Trojan hero.

Vergilius' *Aeneid*, a most celebrated Latin poem. In it, we see a Sibyl, a cave and a lake. We see necromantic rituals. We see a commotion of the earth. And we get into an Otherworld.

All of that cannot but recall to our minds the legendary setting which lives in the Sibillini Mountain Range. Is there any relation between the narrative written by Vergilius and the mythical lore which inhabits the central Apennines? And if so, why?

We will see that all the listed questions will be given their correct, illuminating, satisfactory answers.

But the time has not yet come for us to provide those answers. We need to proceed with our travel into the legendary tales which narrate of entryways to the Otherworld. Be it the dark world of the dead, or of the demons.

We are now about to leave the great poets of the past, the ancient Greeks, the Roman empire and the classical antiquity. We are going to enter the new era of Christianity. And we will meet other passageways into ghastly Netherworlds.

Netherworlds of demons.

3.3 The otherworldly vision of Saul of Tarsus

With the advent of the new Christian era, men began to dream of travels to the afterlife in a different way. And the drive for a new vision of the Otherworld was provided by Saul of Tarsus, or St. Paul the Apostle.

In his second epistle to the Corinthians, a text which already appears in third-century Papyrus 46, discovered in Cairo, Egypt, and now preserved at the University of Michigan, St. Paul included a most famous reference to his personal experience of a visionary journey into the Christian afterlife (2 Cor, 12, 1-6):

«It is not expedient for me doubtless to glory. I will come to visions and revelations of the Lord. I knew a man in Christ above fourteen years ago

who was caught up to the third heaven (whether in the body, I cannot tell; or whether out of the body, I cannot tell: God knoweth). And I knew such a man [...]. How that he was caught up into paradise, and heard unspeakable words, which it is not lawful for a man to utter. Of such an one will I glory: yet of myself I will not glory, but in mine infirmities. For though I would desire to glory, I shall not be a fool; for I will say the truth [...]]».

Fig. 30 - The excerpt on St. Paul's vision from 2 Cor 12, 1-6 as contained in Papyrus 46 (P. Mich. inv. no. 6238, folium 142r) preserved at the Papyrus Collection of the University of Michigan

In this famous excerpt, which we also read from folium 1486 of the *Codex Vaticanus* (Vat. Gr. 1209), preserved at the Vatican Apostolic Library, a precious fourth-century manuscript bearing the oldest extant specimen of

the New Testament, in the original Greek version, St. Paul announced that he had travelled to Paradise, be it in a vision of in actual reality. And his words opened the way to centuries and centuries of literary narratives, through which Christianity has been developing its own visionary descriptions of the secrets and revelations that the Apostle had seen and learned during his mystical journey, with manifold visions of the Heaven and Hell which were attributed to St. Paul himself or to other later, medieval epigones.

Fig. 31 - St. Paul and his vision of Paradise from 2 Cor 12, 1-6 as it appears in the *Codex Vaticanus* (Vat. Gr. 1209), preserved at the Vatican Apostolic Library in Rome, folium 1486

Nonetheless, the *Visio Sancti Pauli Apostoli*, a sort of elaborated offspring arising from the few words contained in the second epistle to the Corinthians, is probably the most antique instance of a travel into the Otherworld which is to be retrieved in the whole corpus of the Christian

literature and tradition. Its original version in Greek and additional versions in Coptic possibly date as far back as the third century. The first Latin translations were readied after the fifth century, when a more elaborated Greek instance began to circulate, containing a 'Tarsus preface' and a full description of both Heaven and Hell: from this a longer Latin version of the *Visio Sancti Pauli* was drawn, which is found in manuscript NAL 1631, dating to the eighth century and preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France. In the subsequent centuries, a wide circulation was experienced by a shortened Latin version which included only the visit to Hell, possibly edited by Irish monks starting from the ninth century. A full illustration of the story of the manuscripts of this fascinating text can be read in Dario Bullitta's essay *Páls Leizla - The Vision of St. Paul* (London, 2017).

Fig. 32 - The opening page of the *Visio Sancti Pauli* (manuscript NAL 1631, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 2v)

With the *Visio Sancti Pauli*, the long history of the legendary travels of the Christian-era into the Otherworld begins: a journey that will include poetical masterpieces such as the *Divine Comedy* by Dante Alighieri, who certainly was strongly influenced by this apocryphal work.

Now the new Christian journeys into the Otherworld are not carried out in search of the ghosts of the dead, necromantically conjured up and queried in their capacity as seers, in an effort to get a glimpse of one's own future: instead, the grim travels to the other side are now intended to provide the living men with a ghastly warning on what is expecting them at the end of their earthly lives. A warning that is brought back to the world of the living by appalled, converted witnesses to the eternal punishments, like Saul of Tarsus.

In the *Visio Sancti Pauli*, after a vision of the judgment of the souls of the mortals following their death, St. Paul is led by an angel to the holy land of Paradise. And, afterwards, it comes for the Apostle the ghastly hour to visit the demonic region in which harrowing punishments are bestowed on the damned:

Fig. 33 - The excerpts on St. Paul's mystical flight from the *Visio Sancti Pauli* (manuscript NAL 1631, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folia 15r and 15v)

«... He led me over the ocean which supports the foundations of the skies [...] through the sunset, and I could behold the fundament of the sky based

on a great river of water [...] here is the ocean which surrounds the whole earth [...] no light was to be seen there, only darkness and sadness and dreariness».

[In the original Latin text: «... Duxit me super oceanum qui portat fundamenta celi [...] per occasum solis, et vidi principium celi fundatum super flumine aque magno [...] hic est oceanus qui circuit omnem terram [...] non erat lumen in illo loco, sed tenebre et tristitia et mesticia»].

In this gloomy setting, which reminds us of another passageway to the Otherworld, Homer's land of Cimmerians as visited by Odysseus, St. Paul the Apostle begins his blood-curdling travel into Hell:

«And I saw a river foaming with fire, and a throng of men and women who entered the river and immersed themselves up to their knees, and other men up to their navel [...] and other up to their hair [...] And I saw abysses of great depth, and many souls in them [...] they were crying and screaming and saying: O Lord, have mercy upon us [...] There I saw a man being smothered by fiendish angels who waved in their hands triangular tools of metal which they used to pierce the bowels of that old man [...] And nearby I saw another elderly man whom four evil angels were hastening into a run [...] and were throwing stones at him and hurting him in the face as if it were a storm [...] And in the same place I saw many other pits, and a river full of a multitude of men and women, and worms were eating them up [...] And I saw other men and women hung up by their eyebrows and hair and were dragged away by the river of fire...».

[In the original Latin text: «Et vidi illic fluvium ignis ferventem, et ingressus multitudo virorum et mulierum dimersus usque ad ienua et alios viros usque ad ubilicum [...] Alios autem usque ad capillos [...] Et vidi foveas in profundo valde, et in eas animas plurimas [...] Et vidi eas gementes et flentes et dicentes: Miserere nobis, domine [...] Vidi illic hominem subfocari ab angelos tartarucos abentes in manibus suis ferrum trium angulorum de quo perfodiebant viscera senis illius [...] Et vidi non longe alium senem quem adducebant currentes cum festinatione quatuor angeli maligni [...] Et lapidibus percuciebant eum et vulnerabant faciem eius sicut procella [...] Et vidi aliam multitudinem fovearum in eodem loco, et in medium illius flumen repletum multitudine virorum et mulierum et

vermes comedebant eos [...] et vidi alios viros ac mulieres suspensos a superciliis et capillis suis et igneum flumen traebat eos...»].

Fig. 34 - Sinners and harrowing punishments from the *Visio Sancti Pauli* (manuscript NAL 1631, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folia 15v, 16r and 16v)

And the manuscript proceeds on the same grisly tone for many vellum leaves, so depicting a fully horryfying portrait of Christian Hell, with specific punishments attributed to each particular class of sinners, including fornicators, usurers, traitors, heretics, and many others. Nothing the like had ever been sketched before in the Western world.

This gruesome description of horrible punishments being inflicted to the damned by demonic angels and allegedly reported by an Apostle was so emotionally striking that it paved the way, in the subsequent centuries, to a whole series of similar legendary travels into the Otherworld of the Christians. And we are aware that it is like if we were reading excerpts drawn from the *Inferno* depicted by Dante Alighieri: instead, these passages, grisly and unpoetical as they are, are contained in the *Visio Sancti*

Pauli, whose original source dates back to nearly a thousand years before the *Divine Comedy* was even conceived.

So the *Visio Sancti Pauli* is the first amazing instance, set at the very beginning of the Early Middle Ages, of an attempt to define a possible access to the Otherworld, at least as a visionary experience. Later versions of it, such as a French adapted translation contained in a gorgeous fourteenth-century manuscript (MS 020, preserved at the Corpus Christi College in Cambridge) will also include the most famous 'test bridge', a typical specimen which will be repeatedly found in the visionary narratives about otherworldly travels.

Fig. 35 - A impressive miniature portraying the 'test bridge' as found in a fourteenth-century French version of the *Visio Sancti Pauli* (manuscript MS020 preserved at the Corpus Christi College, Cambridge, folium 62r)

Is this visionary experience wholly independent of a potential placement, in a specific spot of our world, of the passageway leading to the inner regions of Hell?

No. The *Visio Sancti Pauli* seems to propose a possible location for its Hell, as St. Paul is told by his accompanying angel:

«The abyss has no bottom [...] And it is like that: if by chance anybody takes a stone and lets it fall in a pit of extreme depth and after many hours it reaches the bottom, such is the abyss».

[In the original Latin text: «Abyssus mensuram non habet [...] et ita est ut si forte aliquis accipiat lapidem et mittat in puteum valde profundum et post multarum orarum perveniat ad terram, sic est abyssus»].

Fig. 36 - Hell as a bottomless abyss from the *Visio Sancti Pauli* (manuscript NAL 1631, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 16r)

The Hell, the Christian Hell inhabited by demons is to be found beneath the ground, within abominable and bottomless subterranean abysses. Ghastly, blood-curdling caverns, just like Vergil's Otherworld in the *Aeneid*.

«Men who were born in the blindness of this world of exile, when they hear talks of eternal, invisible things, they doubt about their true existence because they only know about the lower, earthly world in which they were born».

[In the original Latin text: «Ita in hac exsili sui caecitate nati homines, dum esse summa et invisibilia audiunt, diffidunt an vera sint, quia sola haec infima in quibus nati sunt visibilia noverunt»].

Fig. 38 - The first page of St. Gregory's *Dialogues* (manuscript no. 484/21 preserved at the Rosenbach Museum and Library, Free Library of Philadelphia, Philadelphia, folium 1r)

This is the opening of Book IV of the *Dialogues*, written by Pope St. Gregory I the Great at the end of the sixth century. A book which is fully dedicated to the afterlife and its manifestation to the terrified gaze of living men: the existence and persistence of human soul, its separation from the

physical body, its ultimate destiny. And glimpses, appalling as they might be, of an Otherworld of punishments, a Hell of flames and demons.

As we already saw in the *Visio Sancti Pauli*, in St. Gregory's journeys to the afterlife there will be no heroes searching for oracular advice anymore, but only witnesses to the ghastly retribution that Almighty God has readied for the wicked and the sinner, after their death.

In his work, Gregory provides a number of examples of souls of holy monks and virgins and martyrs having departed from their dead bodies in ghostly appearances, amid heavenly radiances and perfumed smells.

However, there are souls, too, which are not welcomed in Heaven, as Gregory highlights in Chapter XXIX:

«If you believed from the holy writings that the souls of the saints are to be rewarded in heaven, so you should also believe that the souls of the wicked be in hell, because if this reward is bestowed on the just by the eternal justice, and the righteous rejoices in it, so the wicked at the same justice should be grieved and tormented: for as heavenly felicity is bestowed on the elect, so we ought to believe that, from the day of their departure, fire afflicts and burns the reprobate».

Fig. 39 - The final destiny of the just and the wicked from St. Gregory's *Dialogues* (manuscript no. 484/21 preserved at the Rosenbach Museum and Library, Free Library of Philadelphia, Philadelphia, folia 106v and 107r)

[In the original Latin text: «Si esse sanctorum animas in coelo sacri eloquii satisfactione credidisti, oportet ut per omnia esse credas et iniquorum animas in inferno, quia ex retributione eterne iustitiae, ex qua iam iusti gloriantur, necesse est per omnia ut et iniusti crucientur. Nam sicut electos beatitudo laetificat, ita credi necesse est quod a die exitus sui ignis reprobos exurat»].

Has any mortal man ever seen the excruciating punishments delivered in Hell to the wicked? Yes, according to Gregory, because it is God's will that a few men may bear witness of what awaits mankind after crossing the barriers of death:

«For God, out of his great and bountiful mercy, so disposed, that some after their death do suddenly return again to life, and having seen the torments of hell, which previously when they heard of they would not believe, they may now at least tremble at, after they have beheld them with their own eyes».

[In the original Latin text: «Superna enim pietas ex magna misericordiae suae largitate disponit, ut nonnulli etiam post exitum repente ad corpus redeant, et tormenta inferni, quae audita non crediderant, saltem visa pertimescant»].

Fig. 40 - Afterlife experiences as presented in St. Gregory's *Dialogues* (manuscript no. 484/21 preserved at the Rosenbach Museum and Library, Free Library of Philadelphia, Philadelphia, folium 111v)

Gregory's literary narrative is based on visions of the afterlife reported by men who passed away and then returned to life, without the need for a physical entrypoint to the Otherworld, as we found instead in the *Odyssey*

and the “Aeneid”. And the main accounts of this kind provided in the *Dialogues* are the famous excerpts taken from Chapter XXXVI:

«Peter, a monk born in Spain, [...] by a certain sickness he died, and was straightways restored to life again, affirming that he had seen the torments and innumerable places of hell, and many people, who were mighty men in this world, hanging in those flames; and that as himself was carried to be thrown also into the same fire...».

[In the original Latin text: «Petrus quidam monachus ex regione ortus Iberiae, [...] molestia corporis interveniente defunctus est: sed protinus corpori restitutus, inferni supplicia atque innumera loca flammaram se vidisse testabatur. Qui etiam quosdam hujus saeculi potentes in eisdem flammis suspensos se vidisse narrabat. Qui cum jam ductus esset ut in illas et ipse mergeretur...»].

Fig. 41 - The hellish vision of Peter the monk from St. Gregory's *Dialogues* (manuscript no. 484/21 preserved at the Rosenbach Museum and Library, Free Library of Philadelphia, Philadelphia, folia 111v and 112r)

Now the Otherworld is not inhabited by the sorrowful shadows of the dead anymore, but by the pain-stricken souls of those who perished in sin, now burning amid demonic flames. And the new Christian afterlife also houses very special devices to test the dead and their specific wickedness, as detailed in this further excerpt, drawn from Chapters XXXVIII and XXXIX:

«A certain soldier being also brought to the point of death, his soul was in such sort carried out of his body, that he lay void of all sense and feeling, but coming quickly again to himself, he told them that were present, what strange things he had seen. For he said [...] that there was a bridge, under which a black river was flowing, which was sending out vapours of foggy, unbearable stench. After the bridge, a charming grassland full of greenery was visible [...] In that bridge was actually a trial: everybody who attempted to cross with a faulty soul would slip and fall in the gloomy, stinky waters; the righteous, with an unblemished soul, would safely enter the bridge and freely cross it to reach the delightful vision. [...] He saw the just crossing over a bridge to a beautiful place, because the path that leads to eternal life is extremely narrow».

Hec uero erat imprecato ponte pluitio. ut quisquis
per eum iniustorum uellet transire. in tenebroso fetentis
fluuio laberetur. Iusti uero quibus culpa non obstitere. securo
per eum gressu ac libero ad loca amena peruenirent. Ibi

pontem ut quidam fluuium uidit. **GREGORIUS.**
Ex rerum peccatis imaginibus pensam merita causarum.
Per pontem quippe ad amena loca transire iustos aspexit.
quia angusta ualde est semita que ducit ad uitam. Et fetentem

Fig. 42 - The 'test bridge' from St. Gregory's *Dialogues* (manuscript no. 484/21 preserved at the Rosenbach Museum and Library, Free Library of Philadelphia, Philadelphia, folia 112v e 113v)

[In the original Latin text: «Quidam uero miles [...] ad extrema peruenit. Qui eductus in corpore exanimis iacuit, sed citius rediit, et quae cum eo fuerant gesta narrauit. Aiebat enim [...] quia pons erat, sub quo niger atque caliginosus foetores intolerabiles nebulam exhalans fluuius decurrebat.

Transacto autem ponte, amoena erant prata atque virentia [...] Haec vero erat in praedicto ponte probatio ut quisquis per eum injustorum vellet transire, in tenebroso foetentimque fluvio laberetur: justi vero quibus culpa non obsisteret, securo per eum gressu ac libero ad loca amena pervenirent. [...] Per pontem quippe ad amena loca transire iustos aspexit: Quia angusta valde est semita quae ducit ad vitam».]

In the Western culture, this is the first appearance ever of the 'test bridge', an otherworldly contrivance which we described in more detail in our previous article *Antoine de La Sale and the magical bridge concealed beneath Mount Sibyl*, and will find again in other descriptions of the Otherworld as we proceed further in the present research work. As we already saw, the bridge is also contained in later, shortened Latin versions of the *Visio Sancti Pauli*. And we will finally meet it again in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, written in the fifteenth century, one of the two fundamental sources for the legend of the Apennine Sibyl.

Does Pope Gregory the Great just provide mere visions and shreds of dreams about his Christian Otherworld?

No. Gregory is not referring to visions only. He has in mind a specific physical location for his Hell. A place situated in our world, the world of the living. A territory to which a travel can be made in actual reality, in our physical world. And this is in the Italian province of Sicily, with a reference to the volcanic Aeolian Islands, as he states in Chapter XXXV:

Fig. 43 - Sicily and the Aeolian Islands as a possible entryway to Hell, from St. Gregory's *Dialogues* (manuscript no. 484/21 preserved at the Rosenbach Museum and Library, Free Library of Philadelphia, Philadelphia, folium 111r)

«[...] Sicily [...] in the islands of that country there are, more than in any place else, certain gaping gulfs of torments, casting out fire continually. And as it is reported by those who know them, daily do they grow and enlarge themselves: because as the world is drawing on to its end, consequently they swell to collect more people to be burnt there, so much the more do those places of torments open and become wider».

[In the original Latin text: «Quod vero se ad Siciliam duci testatus est, quid sentiri aliud potest, nisi quod prae ceteris locis in ejus terrae insulis eructuante igne tormentorum ollae patuerunt? Quae, ut solent narrare qui noverunt, laxatis cotidie sinibus excrescunt, ut mundi termino appropinquante, quanto certum est illuc amplius exurendos colligi, tanto et eadem tormentorum loca amplius videantur apparere»].

So the age of classical antiquity, with the Avernus of the Cumaean Sibyl, and the new Christian faith, with its volcanic isles, share a same trait on their respective Otherworlds: both seem to be placed at sites where the flames of volcanoes are seen as erupting from the ground, a clear sign of the proximity of a legendary, supernatural abode, like it appears to happen at the Aeolian Islands, in Italy.

Fig. 44 - An impressive view of the volcanic Aeolian Islands, Italy, with Stromboli in the foreground, Panarea in the middle, Salina on the top right and Lipari on the top left

The Otherworld is nothing else but a Netherworld, a subterranean realm of gloom and horror: «we should believe that hell is in the lower parts, under the earth», Gregorius write (in the original Latin text: «quid obstat non video ut sub terra infernus esse credatur», Chapter XLIV. A position already expressed in the *Visio Sancti Pauli*, with its bottomless abysses.

Fig. 45 - A subterranean Hell from St. Gregory's *Dialogues* (manuscript no. 484/21 preserved at the Rosenbach Museum and Library, Free Library of Philadelphia, Philadelphia, folium 118r)

Hell, a realm of subterranean demons. Not different from the fiendish beings which will inhabit the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate, in the Sibillini Mountain Range: a possible legendary location for a hellish abode, too.

3.5 Ireland, the land of medieval otherwordly travels

From Odysseus to Aeneas, and then from St. Paul the Apostle to Pope St. Gregory the Great: in the Western world, the dreams about the Otherworld, the shadows of the dead, the demons and the damned continue to haunt the heart of men for more than a thousand year. In search of an entry point, a passageway to the afterlife, in a yearning effort to get a glimpse of what life might be after one's own death, and in search of warnings and oracular advise.

We are now getting into the central centuries of the Middle Ages, and these dreams are getting darker and darker, with an increasing emphasis on the excruciating character of the punishments being suffered by the souls of the damned, after having been tested for their wickedness.

And the main workshop for the elaboration of gloomy otherwordly visions is Ireland.

Fig. 46 - A gorgeous map of Ireland from a fifteenth-century precious manuscript edition of Ptolemy's *Cosmographia* (Ms-981 réserve from the Bibliothèque de l' Arsenal, now at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 75v)

Why did that secluded, northern-European island become the place of election for the development of narratives concerning visits of mortals to the Otherworld?

We must consider that, since late antiquity and the early Middle Ages, Ireland was already part of Christianity, following the evangelisation process fostered by St. Patrick and other bishops sent there on missionary travels by the Roman Church. And, in Ireland, the new religion had the chance to settle in an environment that was utterly fertile.

Monasteries were established throughout the island following the geography of land-owning noble families. The study of the Greek and Latin traditions and literature flourished and expanded. Clonmacnoise, founded in the sixth century at the very center of Ireland, became a beacon of learning whose renown shone throughout Europe. Clonard Abbey, in

eastern Ireland, attracted thousands of students from both the island itself and abroad. And then Armagh, Swords, Irish-founded Iona on the western coast of Scotland, and many others, took upon themselves the fundamental task to preserve the precious literary heritage which had survived from classical antiquity, a work that was already being performed by the Benedictine abbeys in the European mainland.

Fig. 47 - The ruins of the monastery of Clonmacnoise, County Offaly, Ireland

As a result of this convergence of favourable conditions, Ireland was able to produce manuscripted masterpieces such as ninth-century *Book of Kells*, a gorgeous illuminated manuscript containing the Gospels. Ireland was also the native land of illustrious scholars, like Johannes Scotus Eriugena, the Irish theologian and philosopher who in that same ninth century was the head of the Imperial 'Schola Palatina' in Aachen; and the Irish astronomer Dungal, who discussed the topic of solar eclipses with Emperor Charlemagne. According to Charles Stuart Boswell (*An Irish precursor of Dante*, London, 1908), at that time Ireland was a significant cultural hub

which housed «schools where crowds of students from the surrounding nations found hospitality and instruction»; and the works that the monastic literary tradition produced in Ireland were destined to be transferred to other countries, too, because «the constant flux and reflux of Irish teachers and foreign students necessarily tended to spread abroad so much, at any rate, of the compositions of the Irish schools as was in harmony with the tastes and beliefs of Christendom at large».

Fig. 48 - The opening page of the Gospel of Mark from ninth-century *Book of Kells* (manuscript TCD MS58, Trinity College Library, Dublin, folium 129v)

In this cultural framework, the Irish monasticism began to generate visionary descriptions of journeys into the Otherworld, as such narratives «appear to have possessed a special fascination for the Irish writers», as Boswell says, throughout the centuries of the Middle Ages.

The *Vision of St. Adamnán*. The *Vision of Tnugdalus*. The *Purgatory of St. Patrick*. Dreams of journeys into the Otherworld, with all their ghastly descriptions of demonic punishments and agonising souls of dead men and women. All of them put on parchment in Ireland, or by Irish authors.

It will be those *Visions*, still imaginative travels carried out by frightened witnesses in a sort of Christian nightmare, that will pave the way to a true, material, bodily immersion into the actual horror of Hell. A process which will culminate in the *Purgatory of St. Patrick*.

And Irish scholars, together with their foreign students, will bring such dreadful *Visions*, marked by a gloomy, horrifying hue, outside the remote, secluded territory of Ireland and to all regions of Christian Europe. Including, as we will see, central Italy and the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Fig. 49 - A stunning satellite vision of Ireland as seen by the European Space Agency's satellite Envisat, from a height of 490 miles

3.6 Adamnán and a visionary travel into Hell

«In the main doorway of the city they are confronted by a veil of fire and a veil of ice, smiting perpetually one against the other. The noise and din of these veils, as they clash together, are heard throughout the world, and the seed of Adam, should they hear that din, would be seized thereat with trembling and intolerable dismay».

[In the original Irish text: «Fíal tened ocus fíal d'aigriud i prímdorus inna cathrac inna fiadnaisse...»].

Fig. 50 - The clashing veils of fire and ice portrayed in the *Vision of St. Adamnán* (manuscript 23 E 25 *Lebor na hUidre* or *Book of the Dun Cow*, Royal Irish Academy, Dublin, folium 28)

This is the powerful image with which the Irish *Vision of St. Adamnán* brings us into the ghastly region of the Otherworld, where the reprobates are punished. An image that brings to our mind the ever-slamming metal doors which are found within the inner recesses of the Sibyl's Cave as described, centuries later, by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*.

This *Vision*, written between the tenth century and the eleventh, is the earliest example of the visionary literature which developed in Ireland during the centuries of the Early Middle Ages, a work that relies on preceding works such as the *Visio Sancti Pauli*. In this Irish text, which is found in the famous twelfth-century manuscript called *Lebor na hUidre* (*The Book of the Dun Cow*) preserved at the Royal Irish Academy in Dublin, the soul of St. Adamnán, a cleric who lived in the seventh century, is «departed from out his body [...] and [...] conveyed to the celestial realm, where the heavenly angels are, and to Hell», after having been taken to Land of Saints and the Heavenly Host.

According to the *Vision of St. Adamnán*, the human beings who depart from our world of the living and wait for the Last Judgment cannot join those celestial ranks: the veil of fire and ice separate them from the heavenly realm. And at a gate «sits the Archangel Michael, and with him two youths, with iron rods in their laps to scourge and smite the sinners as they pass through the first grief and torment of the path they have to tread».

Fig. 51 - The Irish words «michel arcaingel» from the *Vision of St. Adamnán* are highlighted (manuscript 23 E 25 *Lebor na hUidre*, Royal Irish Academy, Dublin, folium 28)

From now on, the *Vision of St. Adamnán* presents a list of excruciating torments, through which both the souls of the righteous and the shadows of the wicked must pass, but with utterly contrasting effects. The following is a choice of the pains which are suffered by the sinners, while the righteous pass unscathed:

«A river of fire, its surface an ever-burning flame, lies before that door. [...] A fiery furnace keeps ever burning, its flames reaching a height of twelve thousand cubits; [...] the souls of sinners are baked and scorched therein for twelve years. [...] In that place is a fiery river, which is unlike all other

rivers, for in the midst of it is a strange kind of whirlpool, wherein the souls of the wicked keep turning round and round [...] Twelve fiery dragons swallow up every spirit, one after another, until the lowest dragon lands him in the Devil's maw...».

Fig. 52 - The twelve dragons and the Devil («diabail» in Irish) from the *Vision of St. Adamnán* (manuscript 23 E 25 *Lebor na hUidre*, Royal Irish Academy, Dublin, folium 29)

In the above excerpts fully appears the deliberate effort made by the author of the *Vision* to frighten a terrified audience, with the aim to admonish the faithful on the doom that sinners will meet after their own death. This is the actual edifying target of the visionary narratives elaborated in a Christian cultural environment, ever since the early *Visio Sancti Pauli Apostoli* was written.

In this *Vision of St. Adamnán*, we also stumble upon a sort of old friend, the 'test bridge', which we already found in St. Gregory's *Dialogues* some three

centuries earlier, and in *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* more than three hundred years later:

«A glen, filled with fire, was on the further side of it; huge the flame of it, extending beyond the margin on either hand. [...] Eight serpents were in it, with eyes like coals of fire. An enormous bridge spans the glen, reaching from one bank to the other; high in the middle of it, but lower in its two extremities [...] One company finds the bridge to be of ample width, from beginning to the end, until they win across the fiery glen, safe and sound, fearless and undismayed. The second company, when entering upon it, finds it narrow at first, but broad afterwards [...] But for the last company the bridge is broad at first, but strait and narrow thereafter, until they fall from the midst of it into that same perilous glen, into the throats of those eight red-hot serpents. [...] Now the folk to whom that path was easy were the chaste, the penitent, the diligent [...] They, however, to whom this way was broad at first, but strait thereafter, were sinners».

[In the original Irish text: «Drochet dérmár dan darsin n-glend...»].

Fig. 53 - The magically narrow bridge («drochet» in Irish on the top right) from the *Vision of St. Adamnán* (manuscript 23 E 25 *Lebor na hUidre*, Royal Irish Academy, Dublin, folium 29)

A bridge for the testing of souls. A contrivance we also find in the dark bowels of the Sibyl's Cave, set beneath the peak of Mount Sibyl, in Italy, in a different century and in a different region of Europe.

But let's continue our journey together with St. Adamnán into the Otherworld. We find ourselves, as the author of the *Vision* writes, «in the land of utter darkness», not different from the gloominess we may find in a subterranean abode. Other groups of sinners, including fratricides, thieves, liars, impostors and others, undergo further harrowing punishment, including immersion in «a sea of fire about them up to their chins [...], their faces [...] aflame with agony», tortures inflicted by «demon hosts [...] with fiery clubs in their hands, striking them over the head», «a rough, sharp wind blowing full upon their forehead», «red showers of fire [...] raining on them, every night and every day», and up to the overabundant, awkward image of «throng of demons [...] throttling them, holding in leash the while raw-hided, stinking hounds which they incite to devour and consume them».

Again, the idea of subterranean hollows, this time accompanied by mountains, is reaffirmed: «For this is the nature of it [this land]: mountains, caverns, and thorny brakes [...] Great seas are there, with horrible abysses, wherein is the Devil's constant habitation and abiding place».

Fig. 54 - Hell as caverns and abysses from the *Vision of St. Adamnán* (manuscript 23 E 25 *Lebor na hUidre*, Royal Irish Academy, Dublin, folia 30 and 31)

Finally, Adamnán's soul is sent back into his living body, having been warned to «rehearse [...] in the great congregations of laymen and of clerics, the rewards of Heaven and the pains of Hell, even as his guardian angel had revealed them unto him».

Such are the legendary tales on ghastly journeys to the Otherworld that were originated in Ireland during the early Middle Ages.

As to this specific text, the *Vision of St. Adamnán* did not experience a wide circulation outside Ireland, owing to its original redaction in Irish and not in Latin. As a result, we find this text in a few manuscripts only, though certainly it opened the way to a number of other similar works.

However, the *Vision of St. Adamnán* is not the only one. And the subsequent visions, all produced in an Irish monastic setting, have journeyed across Europe and reached the entire continent, becoming part of a common Western and Christian heritage.

Fig. 55 - Map of Ireland included in Gerardus Mercator's *Atlas sive Cosmographicae Meditationes de Fabrica Mundi et Fabricati Figura*, Duisburg, 1595

An heritage of subterranean regions described as the house of Hell and the abode of fiendish demons. To which, under certain conditions, a legendary access is allowed.

This is also the case of the most-renowned *Vision of Tnugdalus*, with nearly two hundred manuscripts retrieved in many European countries. And we will consider this further Irish tale in the next paragraph.

3.7 Tnugdalus, a living Irish knight facing the eternal punishment

Another visionary narrative came from Ireland during the same centuries: a tale which experienced a much greater circulation across Europe, with more than one hundred seventy manuscripts discovered in different languages. It is the *Vision of Tnugdalus*, written in Latin by an Irish monk at a German monastery and dating to the year 1149. We read this *Vision* from the transcript provided by Albrecht Wagner in 1882 and the manuscript Harley 3776 preserved at the British Library in London, dating to the fourteenth century. Furthermore, we accompany Tnugdalus' journey into the Otherworld with the gorgeous miniatures contained in *Les Visions du chevalier Tondal*, a late fifteenth-century manuscript now at the J. Paul Getty Museum in Los Angeles.

Fig. 56 - Tnugdalus appears to be dead after a seizure, a miniature contained in *Les Visions du chevalier Tondal* (manuscript no. 30 preserved at the Getty Museum, Los Angeles, folium 11)

Tnugdalus, an Irish knight who used to live in the utter disregard of religion, is struck by a sudden infirmity and falls down as dead, remaining in this condition for three days. In this predicament, his soul is driven out of his body and, led by a guiding angel, is taken «to a valley as frightful as gloomy and enshrouded by a fog of death» (in the original Latin text: «ad vallem valde terribilem ac tenebrosam et mortis caligine copertam»). This is the beginning of a ghastly visit to the Otherworld. And not only as a spectator, like St. Paul the Apostle or St. Adamnán, but as a true and unwilling protagonist of the torments to be experienced there.

Fig. 57 - The soul of Tnugdalus is brought to the otherworldly regions from *De vita Tungalii* (manuscript Harley 3776, British Library, London, folium 83r)

In the *Vision of Tnugdalus*, the usual enumeration of excruciating punishments begins, inflicted by hosts of demons to a number of categories of sinners, including murderers, traitors, fornicators, and many others. First, a sort of cauldron in which the souls of the wicked are baked («cooperculum habens ferreum [...] Descendebat enim super illam laminam miserrimarum multitudo animarum et illic cremabantur»).

Fig. 58 - Murderers are baked in a sort of hellish cauldron (a miniature contained in *Les Visions du chevalier Tondal* (manuscript no. 30 preserved at the Getty Museum, Los Angeles, folium 13v)

Subsequently, a tall mountain with one side stenching with sulphur and fire, and the other side icy and hit by horrible winds («ad montem mire magitudinis, magni horroris et vaste solitudinis [...] ex una parte illius intineris ignis putridus, sulphureous atque tenebrosus, ex altera autem parte nix glacialis et cum grandine ventus horribilis»).

Then, again, we find our well-known 'test bridge', a typical otherwordly device which we will retrieve once more in *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* written by Antoine de la Sale centuries later:

«They came to a dark valley, which was deep and utterly rotten, whose bottom no one could discern, yet they could hear the roar of a fiery river and the wailing of many souls from the abyss. [...] A long plank stretched from one mountainous side to the other, a sort of bridge which crossed the valley, one thousand feet long but only one foot in breadth. Nobody was to pass through that bridge if not an elected soul. From it, he saw many souls fall down...».

Fig. 59 - Tnugdalus 'test bridge' from *De vita Tungalii* (manuscript Harley 3776, British Library, London, folium 83r, with slight textual differences with respect to the transcript provided by Albrecht Wagner)

[In the original Latin text: «Venerunt ad vallem valde profundam, putridam nimis ac tenebrosam, cujus profunditatem ipsa quidem anima videre non poterat, sonitum autem sulphurei fluminis et ululatus multitudinis in imis patientis audire valebat. [...] Tabula autem longissima ab uno monte in alium in modum pontis se super vallem extenderat, qui mille passus in longitudine, in latitudine vero unius pedis mensuram habebat. Quem pontem transire nisi electus nemo poterat. De quo vidit multos cadere...»].

Fig. 60 - Tnugdalus is led across the 'test bridge' by his accompanying angel as they appear in *Les Visions du chevalier Tondal* (manuscript no. 30 preserved at the Getty Museum, Los Angeles, folium 15v)

Fig. 61 - A lake inhabited by demonic beasts feeding on souls from *De vita Tungalii* (manuscript Harley 3776, British Library, London, folium 84r, with slight textual differences with respect to the transcript provided by Albrecht Wagner)

The *Vision* continues with a giant beast with jaws full of flames, into which legions of demons pressed the souls («bestiam magnitudinem incredibilem

et horrore intolerabilem [...] Flamma etiam inextinguibilis ex ore ejus eructabat [...] ante cujus os erat etiam immundorum spirituum multitudo qui animas intrare cogebant»), and a stormy lake with agitated waters, inhabited by a multitude of horrifying beasts, which only craved to feed on human souls («stagnum amplum valde et tempestuosum, cujus fluctus astantes non permittebat cernere celum. Inerat etiam ibi plurima multitudo bestiarum terribilium, que mugientes nil aliud poscebant, nis ut animas devorarent»).

And then, another 'test bridge' follows, this time leading through the lake:

«Across the width of it a very narrow bridge stood, its length some two miles, the width of the lake. But the width of the bridge was just one palm, so it was longer and narrower than the one we described above. And this plank was studded with sharpened iron nails...».

[In the original Latin text: «Per latum vero ejus pons multum angustus erat et longus, cujus longitudo quasi per duo miliaria tendebatur; talis enim erat latitudo stagni. Latitudo vero ipsius pontis quasi unius palme mensura. Longior namque et angustior erat, quam pons ille, de quo superior diximus. Erat etiam ista tabula inserta clavis ferreis acutissimis...»].

Fig. 62 - The second 'test bridge' studded with iron nails from *De vita Tungali* (manuscript Harley 3776, British Library, London, folium 84r, with slight textual differences with respect to the transcript provided by Albrecht Wagner)

After a final session of illustrative tortures endured by the poor knight Tnugdalus under the action of demons armed with all sorts of axes, razors, scythes, sickles, augers, hooks and other instruments («cum securibus et cultris et sarmentis et bisacutis cum dolabris et terebris et falcibus acutissimis, cum wangiis et fossoriis et cum ceteris instrumentis...»), and a subsequent list of gory, ever-growing atrocities, which wouldn't be out of place in a contemporary horror movie, the unlucky knight is led to the

nethermost portion of Hell: a large cavern, which contains the Fiend himself, a terrific vision that brings Tnugdalus to the verge of madness.

Fig. 63 - Tnugdalus before the inner recesses of Hell from *Les Visions du chevalier Tondal* (manuscript no. 30 preserved at the Getty Museum, Los Angeles, folium 30v)

But then Tnugdalus is made safe. He is brought to Paradise, a much soothing vision, and, finally, he is restored back into his own body, with the warning that from then on he will have to change his life and bear testimony to what he had been allowed to see of the Otherworld.

Since its first redaction the *Vision of Tnugdalus* immediately experienced a great success all over Europe, possibly out of the language used in the redaction, not Irish but Latin, and the feeling of compassion and horrified fear which is aroused in the reader's heart by the account of the harrowing tortures suffered by the poor knight, though revived in his own body at the end of his horrifying adventure. Not secondarily, it must also be highlighted the gruesome, somewhat grotesque touch that Marcus, the Irish monk who wrote *Tnugdalus*, added to his work: the description of such a variety of cruel, bizarre punishment contrivances certainly contributed to the success of the text among readers of all classes.

And, once again, after the *Vision of St. Adamnán*, the *Vision of Tnugdalus* also reaffirms the possibility to access an Otherworld: a subterranean realm, inhabited by demonic presences. This is still a vision, but physical journeys of living men into the afterlife will soon become part of the Irish monastic literature, and will be submitted to the attention of the whole of Europe.

Time has finally come for the *Purgatory of St. Patrick* to break into the visionary dreams of the Western world.

3.8 *St. Patrick's Purgatory, a terrific entryway*

At the end of the twelfth century something began to change as to the visions concerning frightful travels to the Otherworld. Something that, starting from Ireland, would travel far and wide across Europe, and would have an influence on legends inhabiting the center of Italy, amid the remote ridges of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Earlier, visions were just visions. Men had been dreaming about journeys to the Otherworld at least for two millennia, from Odysseus and Aeneas in classical antiquity, to St. Paul the Apostle and Pope St. Gregory the Great in the early Christian age, to the gory *Vision of St. Adamnán* and *Vision of Tnugdalus* produced in a northern European country, Ireland, in the centuries of the Middle Ages.

But then something happened. Dreams were not dreams anymore. A new tale began to circulate, that living men had been there, into the Otherworld. And it used to happen in actual reality. An actual entryway to the afterlife had been found. In our real world, a passageway existed. And men were allowed to access it. Not after their own death, but right then, in the years of the Middle Ages.

It was Henry of Saltrey, a Cistercian monk from England, who, with his work *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, written around the year 1180, opened the way to the astounding renown of this physical entryway to a mystical, subterranean realm, set in the very same island which had already produced remarkable visions of travels into the Otherworld: Ireland.

Fig. 64 - Henry of Saltrey's introduction to his *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii* as it appears in a manuscript dating to the early thirteenth century (Royal MS 13 B VIII, British Library, London, folium 100v), with slight textual differences with respect to the transcript provided by John Colgan

The *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii* presented a most astounding account of a journey into the Otherworld, set at a specific though isolated spot of Europe, which everybody may envisage to reach for a personal, direct check: Lough Derg, a lake in County Donegal, Ireland. A fact that greatly contributed to the widespread success of this amazing story, preserved in some one hundred fifty manuscripted sources, translated in various European languages and marked by a mighty power of attraction to that remote site. A condition very similar to that experienced by similar legendary sites we know, the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate, lost amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, in Italy.

In the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, which we read from various original manuscripts, with the aid of the transcription edited by John Colgan in 1647, Henry of Saltrey recounts the ancient tale of St. Patrick, who in the fifth century came to Ireland to convert the heathens to the new Christian faith.

Fig. 65 - A view of today's Lough Derg, Co. Donegal, Ireland, with Station Island and the historical site of the Purgatory of St. Patrick

Fig. 66 - The section dedicated to the Purgatory of St. Patrick contained in John Colgan's *Acta sanctorum veteris et maioris Scotiae seu Hiberniae insulae*, Book II (Leuven, 1647)

Despite Patrick's evangelisation efforts, the people of Ireland refused to blindly believe in Jesus Christ and his new religion, unless they were put in condition to behold in actual reality such otherworldly punishments and heavenly bliss that Patrick was telling them of. So the task of achieving the conversion of the Irish seemed to have become nearly impracticable; but it was Jesus himself who came to the missionary's aid:

«Good Lord Jesus Christ manifestly appeared to him [...] He brought St. Patrick to a deserted place; there, he showed to him a round hole in the ground, filled with darkness, and said to him: 'Whoever enters this hole, in true penitence, and armed with a true faith, to stay within for one day and one night, he will be cleaned of all the sins committed in life; and if he goes through it, he will behold not only the punishments of the reprobate, but also the rewards of the holy souls, provided that he conducts himself with a firm faith».

[In the original Latin text: «Pius dominus Iesus Christus ei visibiliter apparuit [...] Sanctum vero Patricium in locum desertum adduxit, et unam fossam rotundam, intrinsecus obscuram ibidem ei ostendit, dicens: 'Quisquis veraciter poenitens, vera fide armatus, fossam eandem ingressus, unius diei, ac noctis moram in ea faceret, ab omnibus purgaretur totius vitae sua peccatis atque per illam transiens, non solum visurus esse tormenta malorum, vero etiam, si in fide constanter egisset, gaudia beatorum'»].

Fig. 67 - The excerpt on the round hole and the words told by Jesus Christ to St. Patrick as it appears in a thirteenth-century manuscript (Latin 5137, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 141r), with slight textual differences with respect to the transcript provided by John Colgan

This is the first hint to the existence of an actual entryway to the Otherworld, a cave which living men can enter to gain an access to the

ghastly visions of a purgatorial Hell. No visions anymore. No more dreams. Now, Hell has turned into an actual truth, which can be experienced at a very special place on Earth, set in Ireland. Through a passageway. A cavern.

By that frightful cave, as narrated by Henry of Saltrey, St. Patrick built a church, and the hole, laying in the cemetery on the eastern side of the new temple, was encircled by a wall («fossam autem praedictam, quae in caemiterio est extra frontem Ecclesiae Orientalem, muro circumdedit»). He also added a door whose key he entrusted to the prior of the new church. The place soon started to attract a multitude of visitors, and became known as 'St. Patrick's Purgatory', because there the sins of men were purged («quoniam homo a peccatis purgatur, locus ille Purgatorium S. Patricij nominatur»).

From the time of St. Patrick on, «many men entered the Purgatory; some of them came back, other died in there» (in the original Latin text: «multi homines Purgatorium intraverunt, quorum alij reversi sunt, alij in ipso perierunt»).

Fig. 68 - The ominous statement on the people who never came back from St. Patrick's Purgatory (Latin 5137, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 141v), with slight textual differences with respect to the transcript provided by John Colgan

So began the great renown of a legendary, yet set in our physical world, passageway to the Otherworld set in a remote region of Ireland, in which a mortal man could see the wonders of the afterlife, and live to tell; or die in it.

Henry of Saltrey included further details on the Purgatory, so adding to its blood-curdling fame. As he writes, visitors were not allowed into the horryfying cave, unless they got a special permission by the Church:

«There is also a custom [...] according to which nobody can enter that Purgatorium if not previously authorised by the Bishop of the diocese [...]

Those who address the Bishop and declare their intention, they must be admonished by the Bishop himself to renounce their resolution, with the warning that many entered that place, but never came back».

[In the original Latin text: «Est autem consuetudo [...] ut Purgatorium illud nullus introeat nisi ad Episcopo, in cuius est Episcopatu, licentiam habeat [...] Qui cum ad Episcopum venerit, et ei propositum suum manifestaverit, prius hortetur eum Episcopus, a tali proposito desistere, dicens quod multi illud introieant, qui nunquam redierunt»].

Fig. 69 - The episcopal permission which is needed to access the Purgatory of St. Patrick (Latin 5137, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 141v), with slight textual differences with respect to the transcript provided by John Colgan

Subsequently the aspiring visitor, having reached the site of the Purgatory with a presentation letter written by the Bishop, received a further warning by the local prior as to the many risks he would incur in the cave («ostendens ei multorum in eo esse periculum»). If the faithful still persisted in his perilous resolve, writes Henry de Saltrey, first he would have to spend fifteen full days inside the church built near the entrance to the Purgatory, in penitential fast, raising prayers to God in sincere repentance for his own sins; afterwards, the visitor would be

accompanied to the Purgatory's entryway by a holy procession led by the prior («cum processione, et littanniis ad ostium Purgatorij demum ducitur»). There, after the opening of the gates, the faithful would be formally requested to restate once again, in front of the whole gathering, his unwavering intention to enter the Otherworld.

After an invitation to cross himself with the sign of Jesus Christ («propriaque manu signum crucis fronti suae imprimens»), he was allowed to proceed and get inside («ingreditur»).

Since the legendary age of the entrance of Aeneas into the Avernus, such were the first occurrences of living men allowed into the gloomy realm of the Otherworld.

Then the doors were immediately closed and locked behind him («moxque a Priore ostium obseratur»). And he was left alone in the Purgatory.

Henry de Saltrey also provides a description of the ultimate, ghastly step:

Fig. 70 - An uncertain return from St. Patrick's Purgatory as described in Henry of Saltrey's *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii* (Royal MS 13 B VIII, British Library, London, folium 102v), with slight textual differences with respect to the transcript provided by John Colgan

«The next day, in the morning, the procession returns to the hole, and the gates are re-opened by the prior: and if the man, having come back from the Purgatory, is found there, with the greatest joy he is brought back to the church [...]; but if at the same hour, the next day, he has not come back and no trace of him is found, being certain of his damnation, the door is locked again, and all return to the church».

[In the original Latin text: «Quae die altera, iterum mane de Ecclesia in fossam regreditur, ostiumque a Priore aperitur, et si homo reversus inventus fuerit, cum gaudio in Ecclesiam deducitur [...]; quod si eadem hora, die altera reversus non apparuerit, certissimi de eius perditione, ostio a Priore obserato universi redeunt»].

This is the horrific description that Henry of Saltrey wrote about the Purgatory of St. Patrick, in Ireland, in 1180. A description that, as we will later see, seems to present a number of similarities with other places we know, namely the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate.

But is that all Henry of Saltrey has to say about this ghastly Purgatory?

Not in the least. His description proceeds further. And it is even more terrific than what we already saw.

3.9 A descent into St. Patrick's Purgatory

We are now about to enter the hideous recesses of the Purgatory of St. Patrick, as they are depicted in the year 1180 by Henry of Saltrey in his “Tractatus”. We are going to cross that otherworldly threshold which, according to the legend, was opened in the land of Ireland before the bewildered eyes of St. Patrick by Jesus Christ himself.

As we saw in the previous paragraph, Henry of Saltrey already presented to us a description of the rituals to be performed by the visitors before they went through the door of the Purgatory, accompanied by a holy procession. Subsequently, the Cistercian monk narrates the tale of Owein, a knight who

dared enter that passageway, and of the blood-curdling wonders he had the chance to behold.

And this tale of Owein, the dauntless knight, became known throughout Europe.

«It happened in our present age, certainly at the time of King Stephen, that a certain knight whose name was Owein, of which we narrate in this work...».

[In the original Latin text: «Contigit autem his temporibus nostris, diebus scilicet Regis Stephani, militem quendam nomine Owein de quo praesens est narratio...»].

Fig. 71 - The narrative about Owein begins in the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii* (manuscript Cotton MS Nero A VII, British Library, London, folium 114r)

'King Stephen', as referred here by Henry of Saltrey, is Stephen of Blois, who was King of England until the year 1154. According to an author who writes in the thirteenth century, Matthew of Paris (“*Chronica Majora*”), the episode of Owein would have occurred in 1153. The knight is also called as 'Ovuen', 'Oenus' and other variations in different manuscripts, as in this excerpt taken from the work written by Matthew of Paris:

«Of knight Oenus who entered the Purgatory being still alive. After the confirmation of the peace treaty between King Stephen and General Henry, as we explained before, a certain knight called Oenus, who had served under King Stephen for many years, asked the King [...] 'to have my sins forgiven, I want to enter the Purgatory of St. Patrick».

[In the original Latin text: «De milite Oeno qui purgatorium vivus intravit. Concordia itaque inter regem Stephanum et ducem Henricum, ut dictum est, confirmata, miles quidam Hoenus nomine qui multis annis sub rege Stephano militaverat, licentia a rege impetrata [...] 'ut peccatorum meorum merear remissionem accipere, purgatorium Sancti Patricii volo intrare'»].

Fig. 72 - Knight Oenus and the Purgatory of St. Patrick as mentioned by Matthew of Paris in the paragraphs dedicated to the year 1153 of his *Chronica Majora* (manuscript no. 026, Corpus Christi College, Cambridge, folium 117v)

According to Henry of Saltrey, Owein went to the Irish Bishop who was in charge for the Purgatory of St. Patrick, and lamented that he was a sinner and had offended God greatly. Being fully repentant, he asked the Bishop that the hardest punishment of all be inflicted to him («poenitentiam omnibus poenitentiis graviorem assumam»). The Bishop immediately stated that he shall cross the gate of the Purgatory of St. Patrick.

So began Owein's travel into the Otherworld. He moved to the church which stood by the Purgatory's entrance, waited there for fifteen days in prayer and fasting, received by the prior the usual advice on the dangers he was about to meet, marked himself with the sign of the cross, and was showed into the subterranean hollow («per concavitatem subterraneam»).

Fig. 73 - Entrance to the Purgatory of St. Patrick from *La tres noble et tres merueilleuse Histoire du purgatoire saint Patrice* (manuscript Français 1544, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 105r)

Now Owein, a living man, has physically entered the Otherworld. The darkness grows ever and ever as he proceeds further («ingravescentibus magis ac magis tenebris, lucem amisit in brevi totius claritatis»). After the entrance, he finds himself in a sort of arched cloister, where fifteen holy men clad in white tunics provide him with an advice which is intended to ensure his safe passage through the punishments of the Purgatory:

«When you will be under the torments, call the name of Our Lord Jesus Christ».

[In the original Latin text: «Cum te cruciaverint, invoca Dominum Iesum Christum»].

Fig. 74 - Owein's invocation of the name of Jesus Christ (manuscript Cotton MS Nero A VII, British Library, London, folium 114v)

We have already heard of this salvific invocation in another work, “Guerrino the Wretch”, written more than two centuries later. But we will come back to it later in this article.

Now, Owein is ready to fight the fiendish inhabitants of the Otherworld. And here they come, an innumerable multitude of demons, who surround him and threaten him as a mortal man who has been so bold as to have come to that place without waiting for the day of his own death («diem mortis expectare noluit») and in his living body («vivendo corpus tuum»).

When the demons propose to bargain his safe return to the world of the living for his soul, and Owein rejects the deal, the tortures begin. The poor knight is thrown into the fire and hung to hooks, but the invocation of the name of Jesus dispels all excruciating sufferings at once.

From now on, the “Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii” presents a sequence of hellish punishments, not dissimilar from the ones we saw in the “Vision of St. Adamnán” and the “Vision of Tnúgdalus”.

First, Owein is dragged by the demons in a gloomy region where a cold wind blows, which seems to pierce his very body («ventus quidem urens ibi afluit, qui vix audiri potuit, sed tamen sui rigiditate corpus suum videbatur perforare»). Then he is shown large, boundless fields full of suffering souls, tormented by fiery nails, demonic whips, and dragons eating up their limbs with jaws of fire. But Owein repeatedly calls the name of Jesus Christ, so he succeeds in avoiding all the listed tortures.

Further fields are shown to Owein which contain souls hung by their feet, hair, arms or heads and submerged in pools of fire, or even forced to swallow liquefied metal.

Then, one of the wondrous contrivances typical of legendary otherworldly narratives makes its appearance:

«A wheel of fire appeared before them, large and huge; to his spokes and rim fiery hooks were set everywhere, from which men were hung. Half of the wheel was up in the air, while the other half immersed itself in the ground; the flame of a frighful, sulfurous fire blazed from the ground near the wheel, and burned miserably the men who were hanged there...».

[In the original Latin text: «Apparuit rota ignea mirae magnitudinis, cuius radij, et canthi uncis igneis erant undique circumsepti, in quibus singuli homines infixi pendebant. Huius autem rotae medietas sursum in aere stabat, alia medietas in terra deorsum mergebatur: flamma vero tetri sulphureique incendij de terra circa rotam surgebat, et in ea pendentis miserime torrebat...»].

Fig. 75 - The hideous wheel of fire in the Purgatory of St. Patrick (Latin 5137, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 143v), with slight textual differences with respect to the transcript provided by John Colgan

And another contrivance we find, that same 'test bridge' which we have stumbled upon so many times in other narratives concerning journeys to the Otherworld, and in Antoine de la Sale's "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl" as well:

«... They arrived at a river which was very large and issued a foul smell, being covered by the flames of a sulfurous fire, and crammed with demons. They said to him: 'Beneath this fiery river is the entrance to Hell'. A bridge spanned across that river».

[In the original Latin text: «... Pervenerunt ad flumen quoddam latissimum et foetidum, totum tanquam sulphurei incendii flammam coopertum, Daemonumque multitudine plenum. Dixерunt ergo ei: sub isto flammante

flumine noveris infernum esse. Ultra flumen illud quod videbatur, pons unus protendebatur»].

Fig. 76 - The otherworldly test bridge set within St. Patrick's Purgatory as described in Henry of Saltrey's *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii* (Royal MS 13 B VIII, British Library, London, folium 105v)

As all the 'test bridges' we know, this specimen, too, gets wider and wider as the true believer in God treads on it:

«That bridge showed three frightful features to those who had to get through: the first was that it was slippery, so that even if it had been wide enough, no one would be able to set its foot firmly onto it; furthermore, it was so narrow and frail that nobody would dare to stand nor tread on it; third, it spanned so much across the air that utterly horrifying it proved to beholders, as they lifted their eyes to its apex. [...] The knight of Jesus [...] cautiously began to tread the bridge, without sensing nothing slippery under his feet, so he could walk confidently along it as he put his full trust in the Lord; and the more he went up, the larger he found the bridge to be; and after a little while so grew the width of the bridge, that eleven wagons travelling at the same time would enjoy enough space [...] He proceeded steadily and saw that the broadness of the bridge was growing so much that scarcely he could now see the two sides of it».

Fig. 77 - The full episode of the test bridge as it appears in a fine fourteenth-century manuscript (Harley 3776, British Library, London, folia 79r and 79v)

[In the original Latin text: «Erant autem in eo tria transeuntibus valde formidanda: Primum quod ita lubricus erat, ut etiamsi latissimus esset, vix aut nullatenus pedem in eo figere posset: Secundum, quod ita strictus erat et gracilis, ut vix aut nullo modo, in eo aliquis stare, vel ambulare posset; Tertium, quod adeo, protendebatur in aere, ut etiam horribile videretur, ad ipsius altitudinem oculos erigere. [...] Miles Christi [...] coepit pedetentim super pontem incedere. Nihil igitur lubrici sub pedibus eius sentiens firmus incedebat in Domino confidens: et quo altius ascendit, eo spatiosiorem pontem invenit; et ecce post paululum, tanta crevit pontis latitudo, ut etiam undecim carra excipere sibi obviantia [...] Securus tandem procedens, vidit latitudinem pontis in tantum excrescere, ut vix ex utraque parte posset aspicere»].

After this final trial, Owein gets into a heavenly region, in which a multitude of holy men praises the Lord with celestial songs, all the torments vanished, piece and harmony ruling everywhere around him: this is the Earthly Paradise, mankind's homeplace from which it was expelled out of disobedience («patria igitur ista, terrestris est paradisus, de qua

propter inobedientiae culpam ejectus est»). And, looking upwards, Owein can see a great golden radiance, the gates of divine Paradise.

Owein has now completed his long, astounding journey into the Otherworld. As a man who has just undergone a new birth, he returns to the Purgatory's entryway. Before leaving the place, at the arched cloister he meets again the fifteen holy men, who address him with the following words:

«We salute you, brother of ours, we know that you got through the punishments, which you stalwartly endured, and you prevailed, so that all of your sins are now purged. And, see, now on your earthly land the light of the dawn is coming; therefore do go up in haste; for if the prior of the church, after solemn celebration of the Mass, arrives at the gates with his holy procession and finds you not, immediately he will believe you are not coming back, and the gates will be locked shut».

[In the original Latin text: «Eia frater noster, scimus quoniam per tormenta, quae viriliter sustinuisti, vicisti, et ab omnibus peccatis tuis purgatus es. Et ecce iam in patria tua, lucis aurora clarescit: ascende igitur quam cito poteris; nam si Prior Ecclesiae post Missarum solemniam, cum processione veniens ad portam, te redeuntem non invenerit, statim de tuo reditu diffidens, obseratam portam redibit»].

So Owein hurries to the gates of the Purgatory of St. Patrick and, as a living man, he is welcomed back by the prior with the utmost joy. He descended into the Otherworld, and lived to tell.

«All such things», writes Henry of Saltrey in his “Tractatus”, «were related by a monk, Gilbert, to an audience formed by many people, including myself, the way Owein himself had told to him» («aec autem omnia cum saepe dictus Girbertus coram multis, me quoque audiente, sicut saepius ab ipso milite audierat, retulisset»). As further specified by Henry of Saltrey, Gilbert of Lincoln had been in acquaintance with Owein during the stay of the former in Ireland.

And Henry de Saltrey had no doubts:

«Some think, he said, that when Owein first entered that place he was in a trance, and he saw all such things in a spiritual vision; but this utterly contradicts what the knight narrated of his experience, as he saw all those things with his corporeal eyes, and steadily referred he had been there in his mortal body».

[In the original Latin text: «Sunt quidam (inquit) qui dicunt quod aulam intrans primo fuerat in extasi, et haec omnia in spiritu videre: quod omnino sibi miles contigisse contradicit, sed corporeis oculis se vidisse et corporaliter pertulisse constantissime testatur»].

Fig. 78 - The truth in the words narrated by the monk Gilbert as referred by Henry of Saltrey (Royal MS 13 B VIII, British Library, London, folium 111r)

But we still need to pinpoint a detail of great importance, which Henry of Saltrey does not explain: where is that Purgatory's of St. Patrick situated?

We know that it is in Ireland. And, as we will see later, it is located at Lough Derg, a lake in County Donegal, Ireland.

A cave and a lake. And a physical passageway to Hell. A most interesting configuration in the framework of our research on the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate, in the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range.

Let's explore in more detail the site of the Purgatory of St. Patrick. In search of clues which may prove to be most promising for our investigation on the sibilline legends.

Michele Sanvico

END OF PART 1

**Please refer to Part 2
for the continuation of this research paper**